

Filip De DECKER
Marie Skłodowska-Curie
European Fellowship holder,
Università di Verona

The use of the modal particle in *Iliad* 2,1-493

ABSTRACT.— In this article I discuss the use of the modal particle (MP) in *Iliad* 2,1-493 (the part before the *Catalogue of Ships* starts). This part of the book describes Agamemnon's (failed) attempts to rouse the army and Odysseus' intervention to restore Agamemnon's blunder(s). In these lines there are 112 modal indicatives, subjunctive and optative forms, of which 32 with an MP and 80 without it, and provide a small but reliable corpus of instances in different constructions and are therefore sufficient to serve as basis for an investigation and can be used to check if results acquired in other investigations can be confirmed or refuted. I start by outlining how I catalogue the forms, paying particular attention to the overlap between subjunctive and future forms and the metrically and (in writing) equivalent forms, then I list the forms per part of text (speech versus narrative), tense and mood, and type of sentence (main or subordinate), before proceeding to the actual analysis. Time and space constraints prevent me from discussing the previous scholarship on the etymology, origin, meaning and use of the MP in detail, but my working hypothesis is based on ALLAN's (2013) three modal axes and the findings of HARTUNG, VON BÄUMLEIN, MONRO and CHANTRAINE, which can be summarised as follows: the MP is incompatible with Allan's jussive axis and was used in specific instances with a link to the present situation, and was omitted in generic statements, descriptions of repeated actions or in an instance referring to the more remote future. This investigation confirms this hypothesis, but also lists and addresses the exceptions.

1. Brief overview of previous scholarship on the MP

The following explanations have been given for the use of the MP in Homer:¹

1) "Dubitative"

1.1) One of the first suggestions was that the particle could be used to add some doubts to the statement.²

1.2) This explanation might explain the use of the particle, but not its absence.

¹ The most recent surveys are GERÖ (2000), COLVIN (2012) and DE MOL (2015). It was not addressed in the Oxford or Cambridge Commentaries. In the new *Basel Kommentar*, instances with MP are discussed (as e.g. *Iliad* 1,60 and 1,64), but the absence is not (see following note).

² This had been noted in the very early treatises by DEVARIUS (1587: 45, edited by KLOTZ in KLOTZ & DEVARIUS 1835: 26) and HOOGEVEEN (1769, edited by SCHÜTZ in HOOGEVEEN & SCHÜTZ 1813: 30-34) and in BUTTMANN (1810: 496-497, 1819: 323) and AKEN (1861: 55-56, about the potential and unreal in the indicative). It has been reiterated by LATACZ & NÜNLIST & STOEVESSANDT (2002: 51 *betont die Potentialität noch stärker als ohne*).

2) “Conditional”

2.1) The second explanation was that it described the conditions under which the action occurred and that it was used in sentences with a conditional meaning.³

2.2) The problem with this assumption is that it does not explain why the particle is missing in some conditional clauses and relative clauses with a quasi-conditional meaning.

3) Specific versus generic

3.1) The third explanation was that the particle was used in sentences that referred to a specific instance and that it remained absent in generic statements. This explanation, first made by HARTUNG (1832: 294-297) and VON BÄUMLEIN (1846: 208-245, especially 219-220), was reiterated by Delbrück (who added that the prospective subjunctive could be used with an MP, but the volutative one – i.e. the one used in wishes and exhortations – could not)⁴ and accepted by the standard Homeric grammars of MONRO and CHANTRAINE and scholars after them.⁵

3.2) This explanation seems convincing, but the number of exceptions is considerable and they cannot all be emended away by changing $\tau\epsilon$ into $\kappa\epsilon$ and vice versa (as MONRO (1891: 259, 266-267) tried to do). RUIJGH (1971: 286-288) showed that many instances Monro considered to be generic and to be in need in for correction, were not (but this does not explain all the exceptions). Assuming a common origin for $\tau\epsilon$ and $\kappa\epsilon$ does not solve this issue either and would only account for the fact that these two particles never co-occur.

4) Very early on, there were doubts as to the exact meaning and use. Already VON BÄUMLEIN (1846: 216-217), who argued that there was a distinction between generic and specific instances, stated that there were many contexts in which one could not distinguish between the forms with and without MP. The validity of this “particularising theory” was doubted, because there were too many exceptions to the rule,⁶ and therefore the use of the MP was considered to be “poetic” or “metrically motivated”.⁷ The metrical explanation can always be invoked in Homer⁸ and there are several instances in which the particle is not metrically secure; yet, this theory does not explain why in some instances $\kappa(\epsilon)$ was used and in other $\tau(\epsilon)$,

³ See already von THIERSCH (1818: 533-538), ROST (1826: 455-457), MATTHIÄ (1827: 981, 1195), BERNHARDY (1829: 397), HERMANN (1831) and in 1832 in the *Philological Museum* on page 102 (the author is only known by his initials H.M.), AHRENS (1852: 194-195), AKEN (1865: 27-30), WILHELMI (1881: 23).

⁴ DELBRÜCK (1871: 83-86), but his explanation was somewhat unclear as he also spoke about *das Eintreten der Handlung*, but on page 86 he stated that the particle was much more absent in generic statements than in specific ones. See also GILDERSLEEVE (1882), who applied it to Pindar.

⁵ MONRO (1891: 250, 259, 266, 327-335), KÜHNER & GERTH (1898: 208), LEAF (1900: 17), BRUGMANN (1900: 499), CHANTRAINE (1948: 279, 1953: 210-211), SCHWYZER & DEBRUNNER (1950: 305-306), VALGIGLIO (1955: 50), RUIJGH (1971 *passim* but especially page 275 and pages 286-302, 1992: 80-82), DUNKEL (1990, 2014b: 33-35, 397, 430), WAKKER (1994: 207-209 with reference to MONRO, BASSET and RUIJGH).— Surprisingly enough, the issue was not addressed in JACQUINOD (2017).

⁶ HOWORTH (1958), BASSET (1988: 29, 1989: 205); WILLMOTT (2007: 199-210). See also above. Many exceptions involve the use of the so-called *$\tau\epsilon$ -épique*. CHANTRAINE (1953: 349) had some reservations on the “particularising” meaning (in spite of his own analyses), as did GONDA (1956: 147-148), but he did not ascribe his doubts to the number of exceptions.

⁷ Already DEVARIUS (1587: 46, KLOTZ & DEVARIUS 1835: 27), HERMANN (1831: 143) and later EBELING (1885: 692) had observed this. WAKKER (1994: 207) admitted that the metre played a role, but did not consider it to be the sole factor.

⁸ The metre has been used as explanation for the augment use, the use of the tenses and the use of the dual. In all of these instances, the metre played – in my opinion – only a limited role.

both being metrically equivalent. Many commentaries and lexica mention “wohl, zwar” as meaning, but do not discuss when it was used and when it remained absent.⁹

5) Emphatic value

5.1) Other scholars assumed the MP (especially ἄν, cf. supra) had an emphatic value.¹⁰ CAMERER (1968) ascribed an *emphatischen Grundwert* to ἄν and GERÖ (2000) analysed it as “intensional” (*sic*). This was also assumed for non-Homeric Greek: in her study on the ὅπως clauses in Attic, AMIGUES (1977: 142-169) argued that ὅπως ἄν with the subjunctive was more emphatic and outspoken than the simple ὅπως with the subjunctive.

5.2) There is one important shortcoming, however: if the meaning were indeed intensive or emphatic, one would expect the particle to occur with exhortative subjunctives and in wishes, but these subjunctives are almost never constructed with an MP. Moreover, AMIGUES’ explanation of ὅπως ἄν as being the more emphatic form is not necessarily correct: as many instances occur in legal texts (inscriptions) and in oratory, an explanation of the MP as particularising is also possible.¹¹

6) Main versus subordinate clauses

6.1) HOWORTH (1958) observed that the “specific instance theory” had too many exceptions and could therefore not be correct, and suggested that the MP was originally only used in main clauses with verbs referring to a future action; then it could appear in a subordinate clause, but still referred to the verbal action of the main clause, and then finally, it would have spread to the subordinate clauses that did not depend on future actions anymore and it became generalised (as in Attic, where certain clauses generalised the presence and others the absence).

6.2) This cannot account for the examples in which the MP is missing in the main clause nor does it explain why in Homer the MP could be missing and present within the same category (although one could argue that the transition was still in progress). If Howorth’s explanation were correct, one would expect the vast majority of instances in the main clause to have an MP (including the wishes and desiderative forms, cf. infra), but this is not the case.

7) Confronted with the exceptions of the particularising theory, BASSET (1988, 1989: 204-205) adapted the explanation to state that the MP was only used when an action near to the speaker was related (*actualité du locuteur*), but not when actions in a remote past or future were described.

8) Finally, WILLMOTT argued that the particles did not contain any additional meaning and were in the process of being grammaticalised as part of the eventual and potential constructions.¹² This is only partly true; as she stated herself, the MP was used much less in the relative

⁹ A good example is EBELING (1885: 691-735), who described all the uses, but did not discuss the absence. The commentaries by FAESI (1858a, 1858b, see following note) and AMEIS (1870) and AMEIS & HENTZE described the meaning as “wohl”, but do not speak about the examples where the MP is missing.

¹⁰ As can be seen in Faesi’s explanation of *Iliad* 1,137: *die kecke doch gemessene Zuversicht des Sprechenden* (FAESI 1858a: 50); see also CAMERER (1968). The emphatic value seems also accepted in BUTTMANN (1810: 496-497, 1819: 323) and LATACZ & NÜNLIST & STOEVE SANDT (2002: 50,52) where they stated that the MP strengthened the potential value of the optative when used in a protasis and emphasises the expected outcome, when used in a relative clause with final nuance.

¹¹ See already KÜHNER & GERTH (1904: 385-386) and RUIGH (1971: 276). For the use of ὅπως ἄν in inscriptions, see MEISTERHANS (1885: 109). For criticism of AMIGUES’ theory, see also BERS (1984: 164-165).

¹² Willmott (2007: 199-210). Probert (2015: 85) referred to Willmott to state that the presence or absence of the MP did not change the meaning of the relative clause.

clauses with a generic meaning than in those with a specific meaning and in the purpose clauses of the *Odyssey* the MP was more often absent than present.¹³

9) Independent from the exact meaning, it was also noted that in a sequence of optatives and subjunctives the MP usually only appeared with the first form.¹⁴ This is a sort of *conjunction reduction*: if one verb is already marked for particularity, it is not necessary to mark it with the following verb forms.¹⁵

2. Working hypothesis

In his analysis of Greek modality, ALLAN (2013) distinguished three dimensions on which Greek moods are used: deontic (obligation, permission) vs. epistemic (beliefs of the speaker regarding the proposition) modality, speaker vs. event oriented modality and the scale of modality (realis, necessity, possibility and counterfactuality).¹⁶ The Greek subjunctive and optative mood can convey one or more of these dimensions, with the exception of the notion “realis”, which is limited to the indicative only, but which does not mean that the indicative only has the “realis”-meaning. The indicative is also used to indicate the counterfactual and the potential of the past, and is the standard mood for this in Attic Greek. In epic Greek, it is used in this meaning, but the optative can convey this notion as well (I cannot address the co-existence of these two moods here). In what follows, I will investigate in which of ALLAN’s three axes the MP is allowed and will use as working hypothesis a combination of the explanations by HARTUNG – VON BÄUMLEIN and BASSET, which can be summarised as follows: the MP is incompatible with ALLAN’s jussive axis and was used in specific instances with a link to the present situation, and was omitted when the previous verb form had already been marked by it, in generic statements and in the *similia*, descriptions of repeated actions or in an instance referring to the more remote future.¹⁷

¹³ WILLMOTT (2007: 202-204); the data of the purpose clauses could be found in WEBER (1884) already, but she did not quote that book.

¹⁴ VON THIERSCH (1826: 644-645), MADVIG (1847: 152), KRÜGER (1853: 181), BUTTMANN (1854: 401), AKEN (1861: 42, pointing out that this is by no means an absolute rule), GOODWIN (1865: 63-64), FROHBERGER (1867), KÜHNER & GERTH (1898: 248-249), SMYTH & MESSING (1956: 400), RUIGH (1971: 767), RODRÍGUEZ-ADRADOS e.a. (1986: 26), GERÓ (2001: 193).

¹⁵ This principle was first noted for Greek by KIPARSKY (1968), but he did not discuss the MP among the instances of possible reductions.

¹⁶ ALLAN (2013), building on BYBEE & PERKINS & PAGLIUCA (1994), PALMER (2001), NUYTS (2006 – see already NUYTS 2001) and DE HAAN (2006); see also VAN DER AUWERA and PLUNGIAN (1998) for a discussion and definitions. For an application of modality to the Greek moods, see HORROCKS (1995), WILLMOTT (2007), SAMPANIS (2011, 2017), ALLAN (2013), VEKSIKA (2017), MÉNDEZ-DOSUNA (2018: 271).

¹⁷ See also CHANTRAINE (1953: 210-211), *L'étude des exemples nous montrent qu'elles* (sc. the modal particles) *ne s'emploient pas mécaniquement: elles soulignent un cas particulier, marquent une emphase et s'emploient avec le subjonctif éventuel plutôt qu'avec le subjonctif de volonté.*

Before I proceed to the analysis, I first want to outline how I proceeded to tagging the verb forms.

3. The future-subjunctive and future-desiderative forms

The first problem is the distinction between the future indicative and the subjunctive aorist. As is known, the subjunctive aorist of the sigmatic aorist is metrically equivalent to the future indicative (unless the verb is a semi-deponent or belongs to the *verba liquida*) and those forms would have been written the same in the most alphabets anyway: λύσω can be either future indicative or subjunctive aorist, and λύσωσι and λύσουσι are metrically equivalent and would have written ΛΥΣΟΣΙ in the oldest Greek alphabet and in that of Athens from before 403 BC.¹⁸ CHANTRAINE (1953: 225) argued that one should make a difference between the two forms based on the transmission (thus distinguishing λύσωσι from λύσουσι), and consider the form a subjunctive, when an MP is used (1953: 206-21), but in my opinion this fails to take into account the transmission problems (as in several cases both forms are found in the codices) and the fact that in Homer's time one could not have differentiated between the forms (at least in writing). The verbs without an aorist or with a non-sigmatic aorist build their future on the Indo-European desiderative *-(h₁)s-:¹⁹ the verb ἄγω has a reduplicated aorist ἤγαγον with a subjunctive aorist ἀγάγω, but has a future form ἄξω which is built on *h₂eǵ-s-. The same applies to the semi-deponent future forms.²⁰ For that reason I catalogued the forms of the type λύσω as a special category "future-subjunctives".

An additional problem in this discussion is the third person singular ending in -(σ)ει. When a verb form with this ending appears in a main clause (mostly with a modal particle) or in a subordinate clause and is followed by a word that starts with a vowel, -ει is often corrected into -ει' (as was the case for ἀτιμήσει in *Iliad* 9,62, corrected into ἀτιμήσει' by BENTLEY and πείσει in *Iliad* 9,386 which was changed into πείσει' by BARNES 1711: 346; in our corpus

¹⁸ This was also noted in DE MOL (2015: 10-11). In 403/2 BC the Athenian archon Eukleides, on suggestion of Archinos, suggested to adopt the Ionic alphabet with its 24 letters (including the eta and the omega, which the Athenians did not use (regularly) until then). It is that alphabet that will become the "Greek" one in use until today.

¹⁹ For the present investigation it is irrelevant whether the suffix was *-s- or *-h₁s- or whether or not both suffixes existed.

²⁰ Contrary to e.g. WILLI (2011, 2018: 441-447) I believe that the Greek future continues both the subjunctive and the desiderative, or better said, that the old desiderative and the subjunctive of the sigmatic aorist merged in the Greek future. The first one to state that the future originated in the subjunctive were BUTTMANN (1830: 398, 1854: 396) and also AKEN (1865: 13), whereas FRANKE (1861) stated that all future forms were in origin present forms. I cannot address that issue in detail here (already BRUGMANN 1880: 58-64 stated that the issue could not be solved), nor the question whether there is a difference in meaning between the future and the subjunctive aorist forms.

we have for τιμήσει which was transmitted besides τιμήση in *Iliad* 2,3 and changed into τιμήσει' by VOSS 1838: 30 – see below),²¹ but there are several problems with that specific ending. First, we cannot distinguish between the subjunctive ending -η and the “genuine” future ending -ει (as in later Attic), which is the reason why these forms are called “future-subjunctives” here. Second, in West-Ionic the ending -ει was used as subjunctive ending (and even in Doric and Lesbian dialects),²² but whether this means that this ending was a subjunctive in Homer as well, is debated (LA ROCHE 1869: 239-242 emphatically denied this, BRUGMANN 1916: 527-528 remained sceptical as well and later grammarians did not address these forms). As I noted above, the forms in -ει and -η are metrically equivalent, but the fact that Ionic dialects (Ionic being the main component of the epic language) use the “short” vowel variants as genuine subjunctives (cf. *infra* as well), adds to the uncertainty. Third, it has been argued that the ending -ει could be an optative ending as well. Building on SAVELSBERG (1867a: 413-416, 1867b: 507-513), AMEIS (1868c: 52) and AMEIS & HENTZE (1871: 90) argued that this ending was an apocopated variant of the optative ending in -ειε and could occur even before a word starting with a consonant, but at the end of the line and before a consonant such an apocope seems highly unlikely and already VON THIERSCH (1818: 207) stated that the ending -ειε was never elided into -ει, so that all the endings -ει had to be changed into -αι, which is in my opinion at least as unlikely, because it involves changing many transmitted forms. While SAVELSBERG's, AMEIS' and AMEIS & HENTZE's explanations can no longer be sustained, the question remains whether or not the ending -ει could have been used for the optative.²³ LA ROCHE (1869: 242-243) stated with great certainty that this ending did not occur in epic Greek, but the Arcadian dialect has the form διακωλύσει which is often interpreted as an optative.²⁴ If that form is indeed

²¹ There are more examples of this change in the different editions: in the *Iliad* we have 2,4, 4,178, 9,62, 9,386 14,240, 20,102 and 24,672. — In his *Iliad* edition, WEST rejected BENTLEY's correction (1998: 254) for 9,62, but adopted BARNES' (WEST 1998: 269) for 9,386 and referred in both instances to the other instance, although he did not state why he now adopted and then rejected the correction, while VAN THIEL (2011: 156 and 166) was more consistent and preserved the transmitted readings in both instances of *Iliad* 9.

²² WESTPHAL (1868: 69-70, discussing the short vowel subjunctives in general), SCHULZE (1885, with reference to WESTPHAL), SMYTH (1894: 217-218, with reference to SCHULZE 1885), BUCK (1910: 111), BRUGMANN (1900: 333, 1916: 527-528, doubting however whether this meant that one could restore the short endings in Homer), BECHTEL (1924: 217, with reference to SCHULZE 1885), SCHWYZER (1939: 790-791), CHANTRAINE (1964: 259), RIX (1992: 230).

²³ Surprisingly enough, this issue is not addressed in RIX (1992).

²⁴ BRUGMANN (1880: 66-67), SPITZER (1883: 60, but he interpreted the forms as apocope from διακωλύσειε, thus returning to what AMEIS and AMEIS & HENTZE had already argued for), WACKERNAGEL (1897: 46), BECHTEL (1921: 287, a suggestion he already made in 1888), SCHWYZER (1939: 660 and not 656 as CHANTRAINE 1964: 266 stated), CHANTRAINE (1964: 266, with reference to SCHWYZER).

an optative, the optative ending -ει could be accepted for Homer as well (as was cautiously and hesitatingly suggested by WACKERNAGEL 1897: 46), especially since Arcadian is a dialect of the Æolic branch and the epic language has a strong Æolic layer. It would then render it unnecessary to interpret the ending -ει as an elided -ειε when it appears before a caesura (reason why it is often printed as -ει' by editors). Others, however, have tried to explain διακωλύσει as a future (HOFFMANN 1891: 260-261, DUBOIS 1986: 226), or as subjunctive (SLOTTY 1915: 128), and it remains therefore uncertain if it is indeed an optative.²⁵ In favour of interpreting διακωλύσει as an optative, is the fact that subjunctive was not used regularly anymore in Arcadian at the time of that inscription, that the form following διακωλύσει was an optative as well (namely φθέραι),²⁶ and that the combination of a future indicative and an optative was not common at all (as was admitted by DUBOIS 1986: 226 himself). Given the fact that an optative in -ει could have existed in a dialect of the Æolic group and that the epic language has a strong Æolic component, it cannot be excluded either that the ending -ει would in fact be a relic of such an old optative form (although this remains highly controversial). This, combined with the fact that the ending -ει could also be a subjunctive or future-subjunctive ending, makes correcting -ει into -ει' unnecessary, but at the same time it makes it nearly impossible to correctly assess these forms as to mood and tense.— There is only one such instance where -ει appears before a vowel (*Iliad* 2,3), but in that instance other variants are attested as well. This instance will be discussed below in more detail.

An additional special case is the form οἶσω, which in post-epic Greek serves as future for the verb φέρω, but has its own indicative and imperative forms in Homer. As such, one could describe it as a desiderative form, but when we accept the etymology suggested by TICHY (2002), who linked this form with the Latin verb *utor* "I use" and reconstructed **h₃eǵt-*, it cannot be excluded that οἶσω would be a sigmatic formation of this root. For that reason, I catalogued this form as a separate category.

4. Other morphological issues

In two cases it is impossible to determine the exact tense: κρινώμεθ' (385) and διακρίνωσιν (475). Both forms are *verba liquida* with a sigmatic aorist, in which case the present subjunctive and aorist are the same. I therefore catalogued these forms as a subjunctive without the indication of time. There are two more problematic forms (προσαμύνομεν (238) and ἐγείρομεν (440)), which will be addressed below.

²⁵ As CHANTRAINE (1964: 266) added cautiously.

²⁶ This form was quoted in BRUGMANN (1880: 67) and SCHWYZER (1939: 660).

5. The short-vowel subjunctive forms

The forms *προσαμύνομεν* (238) and *ἐγείρομεν* (440) are generally interpreted as short vowel aorist subjunctives. The issue is whether or not they can be considered a present subjunctive as well. Initially, the existence and the origin of the short vowel subjunctives were ascribed to metrical requirements (ROST 1826: 242, BUTTMANN 1830: 352, VOSS 1838: 2, KRÜGER 1853: 6 – they discussed several issues, but in their opinion the forms originated solely by metrical needs). PAECH (1856) and WESTPHAL (1868: 69-70) argued that the short vowel subjunctives could only be used with athematic presents or with the subjunctive of the sigmatic aorist (as this originally had not thematic vowel either). For the exceptions to this rule, they either assumed that the forms were not present subjunctives, but aorist ones or they explained the short vowel subjunctive by the fact that an athematic present existed as well: this could explain short vowel subjunctives such as *βούλεται* (if one accepts the link they suggested with the Latin athematic present form *vult*, which is not certain at all) or *εὔχεται* (as there is an athematic form *εὔκτο*, but the question is if this is a root aorist or an athematic imperfect (i.e. a root present)), but for forms such as *στρέφεται* and *ἐπείγεται* such athematic/root presents are much more difficult to defend. STIER (1869) provided a detailed study of the forms, but did not discuss the origins. Most scholars accepted the theory by PAECH and WESTPHAL, but went one step further and suggested that the thematic presents could not have a short vowel subjunctive.²⁷ The question is whether forms such as *βούλεται*, *στρέφεται* and *ἐπείγεται* need to be removed from the text (these doubts had been raised already by BRUGMANN 1900: 333, 1916: 523 with bibliography, 527-528, 534 and SCHWYZER 1939: 790-791). While I believe that the PAECH-WESTPHAL analysis is by and large correct, one could also assume an analogical levelling in two directions for epic Greek: just as athematic verb forms could take the long vowel subjunctive forms from the thematic ones, thematic verbs could take the short vowel from the athematic and the sigmatic aorist forms. In my opinion less likely, but nevertheless not impossible, would be that in the third person plural endings for the thematic verbs *-ωντι* and *-ωνται* a shortening caused by OSTHOFF's Law occurred, leading to the endings *-οντι* and *-ονται*, which then could have influenced the

²⁷ CURTIUS *apud* STIER (1869: 137) referred to WESTPHAL (1868: 69-70), CURTIUS (1880: 87-90) with a discussion of the Homeric instances, LEAF (1886: 401) on *στρέφεται* in *Iliad* 12,42, MONRO (1891: 71), CHANTRAINE 1948: 454-458, 1964: 259), not stating it explicitly, but de facto ruling out short vowel subjunctive forms in the present thematic stem, RIX (1992: 230), limiting these forms to athematic primary stems and non-Attic non-present forms, even WEST (1998: 8) removed *βούλεται* in *Iliad* 1,67 and changed it into *βούλητ'*, a conjecture by PAYNE KNIGHT (1820: 69) in the *Prolegomena*, 4 in the text and page 4 in the *Notae* – this change necessitates the elision of the short diphthong *-αι* before a caesura, not impossible but infrequent nonetheless, and removes a linguistic peculiarity from the text.

third person singular endings, changing -η into -ει and -ηται into -εται. I consider this less likely, because in my opinion the long vowel endings of the first and second person plural (-ομεν and -ομεθα, and -ητε and -ησθε) would have blocked or analogically restored the long vowel in the third person plural.

This brings us to the two debated forms in our corpus: *προσαμύνομεν* (238) and *ἐγείρομεν* (440). Both of them appear in a context where an indicative is impossible, the former in an indirect question with an MP (although the MP is metrically not entirely secure) and the latter in a purpose clause with an MP. According to the traditional account, this would have to be subjunctive aorists, but as forms such as *βούλεται* and *στρέφεται* act as subjunctive present, it cannot be excluded that *προσαμύνομεν* and *ἐγείρομεν* would have been present forms. Therefore I catalogued them as subjunctives without a specification for tense.

6. Other textually disputed instances

There are two instances in which the codices diverge between an optative, subjunctive, future-subjunctive or future-desiderative. I will discuss them below.

(EX.01) (3) *ἀλλ' ὃ γε μερμήριζε κατὰ φρένα ὡς Ἀχιλλῆα*
(4) *τιμῆση, ὀλέση δὲ πολέας ἐπὶ νηυσὶν Ἀχαιῶν.* (*Iliad* 2,3-4).²⁸

“But he pounded in his heart how he would honour Achilles and kill many at the ships of the Achaeans.”

These two lines describe Zeus thinking about how he could harm the Achaeans and temporarily give the Trojans the upperhand to enact vengeance for Achilles. Besides *τιμῆση*, also *τιμῆσει* is attested in the scholia (which stated *τιμῆσει εὐκτικόν*, implying that it should actually have been *τιμῆσει* from *τιμῆσειε*?) and for *ὀλέση* also *ὀλέσει* has been transmitted. VOSS (1838: 30) suggested to change the first one into *τιμῆσει* (cf. supra) and the second one into *ὀλέσαι* to have two optative forms.²⁹ As I discuss the use of the MP and not the use of the moods (which will have to be done on another occasion), I cannot delve into this too deeply, but I would like to state that the future-subjunctive forms have preference, because they link Zeus' actions with the present. Although the exact meaning of the use of a subjunctive after a secondary tense is still debated, it is generally agreed that the subjunctive is

²⁸ Forms with a modal particle are underlined, forms without one are put in bold face and disputed forms (or forms under discussion) are italicised.

²⁹ Already BENTLEY hinted at this, but in his notes (quoted in MAEHLY 1868: 173 and WRIGHT 1884: 135) he only quoted the scholion that stated that one form was the optative and the other subjunctive.

used after secondary tenses when there is still a connection with the present and/or when the speaker (or narrator) believes that the action can still be accomplished. This use is not limited to purpose clauses, but given the volun-
tative and/or expectative nature of the final clauses, the issue occurs very often in these clauses.³⁰ VOSS' correction aimed at restoring the optative forms is thus unnecessary. Moreover, one could even argue that the forms in -ει had been old optatives to begin with (cf. *supra*).

(EX.02) (33) ἐκ Διός: ἀλλὰ σὺ σῆσιν ἔχε φρεσί, μηδέ σε λήθη

(34) αἰρείτω εὐτ' ἄν σε μελίφρων ὕπνος ἀνήη/ἀνείη. (*Iliad* 2,33-34).

“... from Zeus. But you, keep it in your mind and let forgetfulness not get hold of you, until sweet-thinking sleep has released you.”

In this instance besides the subjunctive ἀνήη, also the form ἀνείη is transmitted, but as this could be either an unusual subjunctive or an optative (in which case it would stand for ἀνείη) and since optatives after primary tense verbs are much rarer than vice versa,³¹ I would prefer the interpretation as a subjunctive. Moreover, the subjunctive with its expectative value suits the

³⁰ Most scholars seem to accept this distinction, as in BUTTMANN (1810: 485-486), VON THIERSCH (1826: 657-659, 681), ROST (1826: 476-477, 481-482), MATTHIAE (1827: 992-1002 for the purpose clauses), BERNHARDY (1829: 401-402), KÜHNER (1835: 487-488), KRÜGER (1859: 102, 147), DELBRÜCK (1871: 83), MONRO (1891: 279-280, describing that the optative is used when immediate fulfilment is not envisaged), AMEIS & HENTZE (1898: 21), CHITIL (1899, who called the subjunctive the *modus energeticus*), MUTZBAUER (1903b: 632), KÜHNER & GERTH (1904: 380-381). CHANTRAINE (1953: 269) pointed out that the subjunctive was more common in purpose clauses than the optative, even after verbs of the past and that the optative was used when there was a link with the past and the fulfilment was less certain (1953: 223, CHANTRAINE & CASEVITZ 2015: 256).— Many have also argued, however, that the traditional distinction (subjunctive after primary tense and optative after secondary tense) was still valid: NOVOTNÝ (1857: 1), CURTIUS (1864: 242, mentioning that the use of the subjunctive after secondary tenses was very rare), and WEBER (1884: 55-56) who argued that when a subjunctive was used after secondary tense, it was still the old paratactic construction. In my opinion that might very well be true, but one could argue that for the optatives after a secondary tense as well, so that the argument does not explain why the subjunctive was used.— The distinctions between subjunctive and optative as described in WILLMOTT (2007) can account for the different uses of the moods as well, as she stated that the subjunctive was in origin a future tense (a statement that I do not necessarily agree with) and that the optative expressed *negative epistemic stance* (although “uncertain epistemic stance” might have been a more suited term, but this is only a terminological discussion). In general, however, her analysis differs much less from earlier scholarship than she claimed it did.

³¹ VON THIERSCH (1826: 619, 659-660), ROST (1826: 478), BERNHARDY (1829: 407-408), KÜHNER (1835: 493-494), KRÜGER (1859: 102), MONRO (1891: 279-280), MUTZBAUER (1903b: 631-632), KÜHNER & GERTH (1904: 428-431), CHANTRAINE (1953: 276-278), CHANTRAINE & CASEVITZ (2015: 310-311).— WEBER (1884: 42-45) was much less convinced and described this use as *so gut wie ausgeschlossen* (page 45).

context (much) better than the optative with its (remotely) possible and volun-
tative meaning.

7. Determining the metrically secure instances of the MP

In two instances the metre cannot guarantee that the transmitted MP is entire-
ly secure, as one can remove it without altering the metre. These instances are:

(EX.03) (226) πλεῖαί τοι χαλκοῦ κλισίαι, πολλαὶ δὲ γυναῖκες
(227) εἰσὶν ἐνὶ κλισίῃς ἐξαίρετοι, ἅς τοι Ἀχαιοὶ
(228) πρωτίστῳ δίδομεν εὔτ' ἂν πτολίεθρον ἔλωμεν. (*Iliad* 2,226-228).³²

“Your tents are full of bronze, there are many women in your tents that
have been chosen for you, whom we the Achaeans give you as first, when we
take a high-built fortress.”

In this instance one could read εὔτε πτολίεθρον instead of εὔτ' ἂν πτολίεθρον
without altering the metre, but as all manuscripts have the MP, I included this
instance in my data.

(EX.04) (235) ὦ πέπονες κάκ' ἐλέγχε' Ἀχαιίδες οὐκέτ' Ἀχαιοὶ
(236) οἴκαδ' ἐπερ σὺν νηυσὶ νεώμεθα, τόνδε δ' ἐῶμεν
(237) αὐτοῦ ἐνὶ Τροίῃ γέρα πεσσέμεν, ὄφρα ἴδῃται
(238) ἦ ῥά τί οἱ χ' ἡμεῖς προσαμύνομεν ἦε καὶ οὐκί: (*Iliad* 2,235-238).

“Oh, you wretches, miserable disgraces, Achaean women, not me, let us re-
turn home with our ships and let us leave him here to gorge on his gifts in Troy,
so that he will see whether we (are the ones that) will protect him or not.”

In this instance the presence of the MP χ' is not entirely secure, because it
could have been added in a period of the epic diction when the *h* of ἡμεῖς no
longer counted as a full consonant. As was the case with the previous in-
stance, I included the instance in my data because all codices have it.

8. Other debated instances

(EX.05) (235) ὦ πέπονες κάκ' ἐλέγχε' Ἀχαιίδες οὐκέτ' Ἀχαιοὶ
(236) οἴκαδ' ἐπερ σὺν νηυσὶ νεώμεθα, τόνδε δ' ἐῶμεν
(237) αὐτοῦ ἐνὶ Τροίῃ γέρα πεσσέμεν, ὄφρα ἴδῃται
(238) ἦ ῥά τί οἱ χ' ἡμεῖς προσαμύνομεν ἦε καὶ οὐκί: (*Iliad* 2,235-238).

“Oh, you wretches, miserable disgraces, Achaean women, not me, let us
return home with our ships and let us leave him here to gorge on his gifts in
Troy, so that he will see whether we (are the ones that) will protect him or not.”

³² In this subchapter the disputed modal particles have been underlined.

In this instance, it is clear that νεώμεθα is a subjunctive, but ἐῶμεν is not so easily analysed. It could be a subjunctive as νεώμεθα and then the meaning would be “and let us leave him here”, but it can also be an indicative in which case it would mean “and we leave him here”. Both are equally possible, but given that νεώμεθα precedes, I preferred to take it as a subjunctive as well.

9. The “negative purpose clauses”

For clauses introduced by μή or a compound of it (but not by e.g. ἵνα μή) I use the category “negative purpose clauses”. These clauses can either be negative purpose clauses, negative wishes or complement clauses after a *verbum timendi*. All these clauses probably go back to a single paratactic construction,³³ namely that of a negative wish “may...not...”: the difference between a negative purpose clause and a negative wish is very small and the *verba timendi* could be interpreted as negative wish clauses in origin (“I fear that Zeus thunders” would then have been “I am afraid. May Zeus not thunder!”) and many negative wishes have a notion of fear in them.³⁴ As it is unclear whether they were perceived as subordinate or main clauses in epic Greek, I created a separate category for it.

10. Data, facts and figures on the MP in our corpus

Now that we have addressed the morphological and textual-critical issues, we can proceed to the analysis. First, I provide the figures of the presence and absence of the MP in our corpus, overall, broken down per mood and tense, per narrative or speech, per type of sentence (main / subordinate).³⁵

	MP	No MP	% MP
SPEECH	29	66	31
NARRATIVE	3	13	
SPEECH INTRODUCTION	0	1	
OVERALL	32	80	29

Table 1: overall data and data per speech, narrative and speech introduction

³³ Discussing the origins of subordination lies outside the scope of this article, as does analysing whether or not all subordinate constructions in *Iliad* 2,1-493 could be interpreted as original paratactic constructions.

³⁴ AKEN (1865: 64-65), DELBRÜCK (1871: 23), WEBER (1884: 4-9), KÜHNER & GERTH (1904: 390-391), HENTZE (1907: 368), CHANTRAINE (1953: 208-209, 288), BRUNEL (1980: 251). See also AMEIS & HENTZE (1901: 87), CHANTRAINE (1953: 208) and FERNÁNDEZ GALIANO (1992: 186) on *Odyssey* 21,324.

³⁵ I only provide a percentage when there are more than 30 instances overall.

	MP	No MP	% MP
MAIN CLAUSE			
SPEECH	11	37	23
NARRATIVE	1	0	
SPEECH INTRODUCTION	0	0	
OVERALL	12	37	24
SUBORDINATE CLAUSES			
SPEECH	18	25	42
NARRATIVE	2	12	
SPEECH INTRODUCTION	0	1	
OVERALL	20	38	34
NEGATIVE PURPOSE CLAUSES			
SPEECH	0	5	
OVERALL	0	5	

**Table 2: data per type of sentence
(main/subordinate and
negative purpose)**

	MP	No MP	% MP
FUTURE-DESIDERATIVE	0	22	
FUTURE-SUBJUNCTIVE	6	17	
* <i>h₃eḡt-</i>	1	0	
SUBJUNCTIVE			
AORIST	8	4	
PRESENT	2	13	
UNDEFINED	3	1	
OVERALL	13	18	42
OPTATIVE			
AORIST	7	12	
PRESENT	4	9	
UNDEFINED	0	0	
OVERALL	11	21	34
INDICATIVE			
AORIST	1	2	

Table 3: Breakdown per tense and mood

	MP	No MP	% MP
TEMPORAL CLAUSES	4	2	
PURPOSE CLAUSES	2	9	
RELATIVE CLAUSES	8	8	
CONDITIONAL CLAUSES	5	15	
AFTER μερμήριζε	0	2	
INDIRECT QUESTIONS	1	2	
OVERALL	20	38	

Table 4: breakdown per type of subordinate clause

11. Results from the data

The facts and figures provide us with the following results, which will be addressed below (and compared to data of a larger corpus).

- 1) There are more instances without an MP than with one.
- 2) The MP is less frequent in the main clause than in subordinate clauses.
- 3) The MP is much more common in speech than in narrative (both in percentages as in absolute figures).
- 4) The future-desiderative forms are incompatible with the MP.
- 5) The future-subjunctive forms take the MP rather infrequently, but the use is not impossible.
- 6) The MP is not found in the negative purpose/negative wish clauses.
- 7) There seem to be only a few instances in a positive purpose clause as well.
- 8) The MP is not frequently used in a conditional clause.

Below I analyse these data, starting with the instances in which the MP is not used, as these are the most frequent ones.

12. The missing instances (1): ALLAN's axis of deontic and jussive

Before proceeding to the actual analysis, it is necessary to observe that in many instances it is difficult, if not impossible, to decide which explanation is possible: especially in cases with a verb in the first person singular or plural, it can be difficult to distinguish between exhortative or simple future meaning, or between a deliberative or simple future meaning. Sometimes exhortative forms are combined with “plain” future forms making the distinction even smaller, as in the example below.

(EX.06) (139) ἀλλ' ἄγεθ' ὡς ἂν ἐγὼ εἶπω **πειθόμεθα** πάντες:

(140) **φεύγωμεν** σὺν νηυσὶ φίλην ἐς πατρίδα γαῖαν:

(141) οὐ γὰρ ἔτι Τροίην **αἰρήσομεν** εὐρύγυιαν. (*Iliad* 2,139-141).

“But well then! Let us all obey what I will say. Let us flee with our ships to (our) beloved fatherland. We will no longer take Troy with its wide streets.”

In this passage I would catalogue *πειθόμεθα* and *φεύγωμεν* as exhortative, because they are preceded by *ἀλλ' ἄγεθ'*, while *αἰρήσομεν* is considered a plain future.

12.1. Exhortative meaning

The MP is missing in exhortative clauses: there are five instances of this (139, 140, 236, 236), four of which have been discussed already (139, 140, 236, 236, 440).

12.2. Negative purpose clauses

In negative wishes, negative purpose clauses,³⁶ and after the *verba timendi* the MP is not used. There are five instances of this (195, 259, 260, 435, 436) and I give one example:

(EX.07) μή τι χολωσάμενος **ῥέξει** κακὸν υἱᾶς Ἀχαιῶν (*Iliad* 2,195).

“May he not do harm to the sons of the Achaeans, because he is enraged.”

The form *ῥέξει* has no MP, because it appears in a negative wish introduced by *μή*.

12.3. Positive purpose clauses

The MP is also unfrequently used in positive purpose clauses. There are nine instances without an MP (206, 232, 237, 282, 282, 299, 359, 363, 381) and two with it (385, 440 – which will be discussed below). This distribution is comparable to that of the *Odyssey*: in that work there are 48 verb forms with an MP in a purpose clause and 267 without one, which means a rate of only 15% MP. In the *Iliad* (without book 10, which is disputed and book 2, which is being addressed here), we have 29 instances of an MP in a purpose clause and 317 without one, which is 8% of forms that have an MP. I give one example.

(EX.08) νῦν δ' ἔρχεσθ' ἐπὶ δεῖπνον ἵνα **ξυνάγωμεν** Ἄρηα (*Iliad* 2,381).

“Now go (back) to dinner, so that we can bring together Ares (sc. our warpower).”

In this example the purpose clause introduced by *ἵνα* has a subjunctive, *ξυνάγωμεν*, without a modal particle. — One could also include the indirect questions and/or constructions after *verba cogitandi* and *verba curandi* in this category.

³⁶ VON THIERSCH (1826: 655-656), ROST (1826: 478-479), WEBER (1884: 32-38), MONRO (1891: 262), CHANTRAINE (1953: 266-273).

(EX.09) (3) ἄλλ' ὃ γε μερμήριζε κατὰ φρένα ὡς Ἀχιλλῆα
 (4) **τιμήση, ὀλέση** δὲ πολέας ἐπὶ νηυσὶν Ἀχαιῶν. (*Iliad* 2,3-4).

“But he pounded in his heart how he would honour Achilles and kill many at the ships of the Achaeans.”

In this example, already discussed because of the textual-critical issues, the interpretation could be manifold: one could argue that the subjunctives appear in a purpose clause “he was thinking in order to...”, but one could also interpret it as indirect deliberative question “he was thinking how he should...” or even as a relative clause “he was thinking in such a way, in a way that...”. Main clause deliberative questions (of which there are no examples in our corpus) tend not to have the modal particle either, but in those instances it is often difficult to distinguish between a form with future reference, one with exhortative meaning or a deliberative question (and in all likelihood the forms had all three notions).

12.4. Wishes

Positive wish clauses do not have the MP either, but there are only two instances of this in our corpus (340, 418). The issue of the (origin of the) wishes will be briefly discussed below.

(EX.10) (340) ἐν πυρὶ δὴ βουλαί τε **γενοίατο** μήδεά τ' ἀνδρῶν
 (341) σπονδαί τ' ἄκρητοι καὶ δεξιαί, ἧς ἐπέπιθμεν: (*Iliad* 2,340-341).

“May the councils and plans of men be given to the fire, and also the un-mixed offerings and our rights hand, in which we trusted.”

The optative *γενοίατο* is a wish and has therefore no modal particle. It has to be admitted that in several instances it is not clear whether one has a potential optative without modal particle, a wish clause or even an exhortative clause. When the sentence is introduced by εἶθε, there is little doubt, but not all wishes are introduced by it.

12.5. Future-desiderative forms.

The next category that is almost completely incompatible with the presence of the MP are the so-called future-desiderative forms. In our corpus there 22 instances (141, 159, 175, 252, 257, 257, 263, 276, 325, 329, 339, 347, 361, 365, 366, 367, 380, 386, 387, 389, 393, 493) and none has an MP. In the *Iliad* (without chants 2 and 10) we have 8 instances with an MP and 351 without it (which is 2%) and in the *Odyssey* there is one instance of future-desiderative with an MP and 300 without it. One example from our corpus can suffice.

- (EX.11) (157) ὦ πόποι αἰγιόχοιο Διὸς τέκος Ἀτρυτώνη,
 (158) οὔτω δὴ οἰκόνδε φίλην ἐς πατρίδα γαῖαν
 (159) Ἀργεῖοι **φεύζονται** ἐπ' εὐρέα νῶτα θαλάσσης (*Iliad* 2,157-159).

“Oh woe (us), daughter of aegis-bearing Zeus, Atrytone, this way the Argives will flee home to their beloved fatherland over the broad surface of the sea.” [NB.: In this passage φεύζονται has no MP, because it is a future-desiderative form.]

12.6. The future-subjunctives

Similarly, the forms catalogued as future-subjunctives appear much more often without MP than with one, although the figures indicate that the MP can be used with a future-subjunctive. We have 17 instances without MP (4, 4 - cf. supra, 73, 74, 147, 193, 195, 203, 253, 261, 328, 367, 379, 388, 390, 395, 436) and 6 with it (72, 83, 258, 364, 391, 488). In the *Iliad* (without 2 and 10) there are 672 instances with an MP and 374 without (16%) and in the *Odyssey* there are 67 instances with and 338 without one (17%). The figures clearly show that there is a preference for not using the MP with these forms, but that the use is not impossible either. I believe that the MP was used much less with these forms than with plain subjunctive forms, because they have both the notion of a subjunctive and a desiderative, but at the same time I suspect that the fact that these forms could be used in contexts where subjunctives and optatives would receive an MP, lead to the expansion of the use to the future-subjunctive forms (this will be discussed later on). I give one example of a future-subjunctive form without MP.

- (EX.12) (73) πρῶτα δ' ἐγὼν ἔπεσιν **πειρήσομαι**, ἢ θέμις ἐστίν,
 (74) καὶ φεύγειν σὺν νηυσὶ πολυκλήϊσι **κελεύσω**:
 (75) ὑμεῖς δ' ἄλλοθεν ἄλλος ἐρητύειν ἐπέεσσιν. (*Iliad* 2,73-74).

“I will try them with words, if this is indeed good use and with order them to flee with their ships full of benches with rowers. You, from one place and another, (try to) restrain them with words.”

In this passage the forms *πειρήσομαι* and *κελεύσω* are future-subjunctive forms and are used without a modal particle.

12.7. Conclusion

The data show that the statement that the MP is incompatible with ALLAN's deontic axis is confirmed: the future-desideratives, the verb forms in purpose and negative purpose clauses and a large part of the future-subjunctive forms do not have the MP, because they have a jussive, voluntative and/or deontic meaning. This also applies to the subjunctives with exhortative meaning in the main clauses, to wishes, to future-desiderative forms and to purpose clauses.

13. The instances without MP (2): the other cases

Now that we have addressed the instances that belong to ALLAN's deontic and jussive axis, we will now proceed to the other instances without modal particle where this explanation alone cannot explain the absence and where the second part of our research hypothesis needs to be tested, namely that verb forms referring to repeated actions, events in a remote past, in generic statements and the *similia*, and when a preceding verb form had already been marked by a modal particle.

13.1. "Particle reduction"

The instances in this last category are relatively easy to analyse. There are seven instances of this so-called "reduction" (81, 126, 127, 251, 251, 364, 488). As was the case with the other reductions, the rule is not absolute, although in our corpus there are no exceptions to it. I give one example of such a reduction (the form with the particle is underlined, the "reduced" forms are put in bold face).

(EX.13) (250) τὼ οὐκ ἂν βασιλῆας ἀνὰ στόμ' ἔχων ἀγορεύοις,

(251) καὶ σφιν ὄνειδέα τε **προφέροις**, νόστον τε **φυλάσσοις**. (*Iliad* 2,250-251).

"That way you would not raise your voice and address the kings, nor would you bring forward insults against them or guard the homecoming."

As the verb ἀγορεύοις has already received a modal particle, προφέροις and φυλάσσοις are used without one.

13.2. Timeless and generic statements, and *similia*

As was noted above, the MP is missing in timeless and generic statements and in *similia*. There are four instances of a subjunctive without a modal particle in a simile in our corpus (147, 294, 395, 475) and one with it (475). In the *Iliad* (as always without Books 2 and 10 here) there are 88 instances without MP and 19 with it in a simile and the *Odyssey* there are 32 instances without MP and 4 with it. The data are clear and this has been noted before,³⁷ but the reason as to why this is the case is not easily found, especially since *similia* compare the story to scenes of everyday life and are thus close to the world of the speaker, hearer and narrator, and do not belong to the remote past nor future (reason why the augment is so common in these passages). In many debated instances, one could, with Monro, change the text (cf. supra), but that does not solve the problem and there are also (a few) instances of *similia* in the speeches. We note, however, that the *similia* in the *Iliad* occur

³⁷ As far as I could establish, it has been noted at least as early as VON THIERSCH (1826: 679).

mostly in narrative (where the MP tends to be absent much more often) and that the poets use *τε-épique* and not the MP, because they describe what RUIJGH called *un fait permanent*.³⁸ That can explain the absence in the generic statements and in some *similia*, but not in all of these instances *τε-épique* appears (in our corpus only in line 475 *τε-épique* has been used).

13.3. Conditional clauses with the optative as old wishes

A special case are the conditional clauses in epic Greek. As had been stated above already, the use of the modal particle in epic Greek was less rigid than that of Attic Greek: in Attic all conditional clauses with a subjunctive *have* to have a modal particle, while those with an optative or indicative *cannot* have one, but in Homeric Greek the situation is less strictly regulated. In spite of this, there are nevertheless some interesting observations that can be made. We note that the optative in the conditional clause very rarely has an MP, whereas a majority of subjunctive clauses does have an MP: the distribution in the *Iliad* is 120 subjunctives in a conditional clause with an MP and 29 without it and 16 optatives with MP and 63 without it (and 23 future-subjunctives with it and 28 without it), and in *Odyssey* there are 56 subjunctives in a conditional have an MP and 28 do not, whereas only 12 optatives have it and 121 do not. At first sight this distribution is very remarkable. If we analyse the conditional clauses with the optative as old wish clauses,³⁹ the absence of the MP could be explained, as wishes do not “take” the MP. In our corpus there is one conditional clause with an optative that has an MP (123) and 8 that do not have it (98, 98, 372, 489, 490, 492 – in 126 and 128 one could argue that the “reduction-rule” caused the absence). Below I discuss two examples.

- (EX.14) (95) τετρήχει δ' ἀγορή, ὑπὸ δὲ στεναχίζετο γαῖα
 (96) λαῶν ἰζόντων, ὄμαδος δ' ἦν: ἐννέα δέ σφεας
 (97) κήρυκες βοόωντες ἐρήτυον, εἴ ποτ' αὐτῆς
 (98) **σχοίατ', ἀκούσειαν** δὲ διοτρεφέων βασιλῆων. (*Iliad* 2,95-98).

“The assembly was in turmoil, the earth groaned beneath it by the people who were sitting on it, there was noise (everywhere), nine heralds were shouting and trying to restrain (the soldiers) so that they would stop their cries and would listen to the kings who are nurtured by Zeus.”

³⁸ RUIJGH (1969, 1971 *passim*).

³⁹ VON THIERSCH (1826: 603-604, 628), KRÜGER (1859: 98), DELBRÜCK (1871: 196), LA ROCHE (1871: 102), LANGE (1872: 326), LEAF (1888: 441), AMEIS & HENTZE (1888: 102), MONRO (1891: 285), SCHWYZER & DEBRUNNER (1950: 320-324), CHANTRAINE (1953: 216), BRÜGGER (2017: 49). See in more detail LANGE (1872, 1873) and CHANTRAINE (1953: 274-279). Traditionally, LANGE (1872, 1873) is considered to be the first to state that the conditional clauses were original wishes, but this had already been stated at least as early as VON THIERSCH (1826: 603-604, 628). TABACHOVITZ (1951), followed by HETRICH (1992:265-266) argued that the conditional clauses had always been subordinated and were never independent paratactic wish clauses.

These lines describe the turmoil in the assembly and how nine heralds (vainly) try to restore calm and order in it to allow the leaders to speak. The conditional clause here can be translated as “to see if, to make that” or “if only they...”. It has the old notion of wish (and also purpose) still in it.

(EX.15) (371) αἶ γὰρ Ζεῦ τε πάτερ καὶ Ἀθηναίη καὶ Ἄπολλον

(372) τοιοῦτοι δέκα μοι συμφράδμονες εἶεν Ἀχαιῶν:

(373) τὼ κε τάχ' ἠμύσειε πόλις Πριάμοιο ἄνακτος

(374) χερσὶν ὕφ' ἠμετέρησιν ἀλοῦσά τε περθομένη τε (*Iliad* 2,371-374).

“If only, oh Father Zeus, Athene and Apollon, there were ten such men among the Achaeans with the same thinking, then soon the city of ruler Priam would have gone down, taken and destroyed by our hands.”

In this specific example the conditional clause is still used in its wish-meaning, but one can see how from this wish-construction, the conditional constructions might have arisen. When we look at the use of the modal particle in the conditional clauses, we get a picture that is not yet the same as in Attic Greek, but one that comes already quite close to it. While subjunctives are relatively frequently used with an MP, an optative in a conditional clause has much less often an MP. In our corpus we have 8 optatives in a conditional clause without an MP and one with it, and in the overall *Iliad* we have 16 optatives with MP and 82 without it in a conditional clause and in the *Odyssey* 12 optatives with and 121 without one. None of the instances with a modal particle is attested in narrative, all of them appear in speeches. One problematic instance in the following instance in the indicative:

(EX.16) (80) εἰ μὲν τις τὸν ὄνειρον Ἀχαιῶν ἄλλος ἔνισπε

(81) ψεῦδος κεν φαῖμεν καὶ νοσφιζοίμεθα μᾶλλον: (*Iliad* 2,80-81).

“If someone else of the Achaeans had told this dream, we would have called it a lie and would have rejected the idea.”

The absence of the particle in νοσφιζοίμεθα can be explained by the reduction rule, but the absence in ἔνισπε is more problematic. From a synchronic Attic point of view there is not anything unusual, since the counterfactual constructions in the indicative always take the modal particle in the main clause or any other subordinate clause, but never in the conditional clause. Even in Homer there are only two instances in which the conditional clause in the indicative has a particle, *Iliad* 23,526 and *Odyssey* 6,282 (but this instance is highly debated and disputed). What is even more remarkable is that the archaic and original use of the optative in the counterfactual construction is still preserved here in the main clause, and also in the subordinate clause, ἔνισπε could still contain an older optative ἐνίσποι. If we explain the condi-

tional clause as an old wish, the absence of the particle can be explained, but even in that scenario we would have to assume that the indicative “intruded” already on the field of the optative in the (remotely) possible and (un)realisable wishes (an issue that cannot be addressed here).

13.4. The other conditional clauses

There is one conditional clause with a (metrically secure) indicative which has no MP, but one can debate whether the conditional clause in this counterfactual construction actually contains a modal indicative. What the conditional clause describes is not something contrary-to-fact, but the opposite: the action of the main clause did not occur, because the action of the conditional clause was completed.⁴⁰ One could therefore catalogue *ἔειπεν* as *realis* and indicative forms in the *realis* do never receive a MP (but even if it were *irrealis*, indicatives in the conditional clauses very exceptionally receive an MP, cf. *supra*).

(EX.17) (155) ἔνθά κεν Ἀργείοισιν ὑπέρμορα νόστος ἐτύχθη
(156) εἰ μὴ Ἀθηναίην Ἦρη πρὸς μῦθον **ἔειπεν** (*Iliad* 2,155-156).

“And then there would have been an homecoming against their fate for the Argives, had Here not spoken a word towards Athene.”

The instances of the optative and indicative in conditional clauses without MP have been addressed, so now we can proceed to the other conditional clauses, where the MP is missing and that have not yet been discussed: 261, 367 and 379 (in 364 the subjunctive has no MP, because it is preceded by another verb that already has an MP and in 387 the verb is a future-desiderative form). In all these three instances the verb is a future-subjunctive and one could assume that the fact the future-subjunctive on itself is enough to make the MP remain absent, but the overall figures of the *Iliad* indicate otherwise: there are 23 future-subjunctive forms with an MP in a conditional clause against 29 without one. That distribution makes assuming that the future-subjunctive form on itself is sufficient for the absence untenable. We will therefore look in more detail into the three instances in our corpus.

(EX.18) (260) μῆδ’ ἔτι Τηλεμάχοιο πατὴρ κεκλημένος εἶην,
(261) εἰ μὴ ἐγὼ σε λαβὼν ἀπὸ μὲν φίλα εἶματα **δύσω**,
(262) χλαῖνάν τ’ ἠδὲ χιτῶνα, τὰ τ’ αἰδῶ ἀμφικαλύπτει,
(263) αὐτὸν δὲ κλαίοντα θοὰς ἐπὶ νῆας **ἀφήσω**
(264) πεπληγῶς ἀγορήθεν ἀεικέσσι πληγῆσιν. (*Iliad* 2,260-264).

⁴⁰ I cannot address the origin of the Greek counterfactual constructions (main and conditional clauses here), and refer to GERTH (1878), KRISCH (1986), RUIJGH (1992), HETTRICH (1998), DE DECKER (2015: 221-240, 2021: §4.4) for different suggestions and analyses.

“May I not be called Telemachus’ father anymore if I do not take your beloved garments, remove your cloak and mantle from you, that cover your private parts, and send you yourself crying away to the fast ships after I hit you away from the assembly with humiliating blows.”

In this instance the absence of the MP with δύσω is problematic, as it clearly refers to a specific instance. One could argue that it is combined with a desiderative form, namely ἀφήσω, and that therefore the form δύσω might have been desiderative itself, but there is no independent evidence for this and therefore this explanation remains speculative.

(EX.19) (367) γνώσει δ’ εἰ καὶ θεσπεσίη πόλιν οὐκ ἀλαπάξεις,
(368) ἢ ἀνδρῶν κακότητι καὶ ἀφραδίῃ πολέμοιο (*Iliad* 2,367-368).

“You will know whether you are not taking/will not take this city by divine power or by the cowardice of your men and their lack of skill in warfare.”

In this specific instance, the absence of the modal particle is quite remarkable, as we are clearly having a specific instance. One could try to change καί into κεν, but then the question remains how the modal particle would have been lost during the transmission. BEKKER (1863: 27-28) suggested to change the future-subjunctive ἀλαπάξεις into the present indicative ἀλαπάξεις, because in his opinion a present reference was needed “whether you are not taking this city...” (this was followed by DÜNTZER 1866: 82, CAUER 1890: 43 and WEST 1998: 60, but not in his own edition, BEKKER 1858: 31). This is not necessary, however, as one could argue that the verb form here has some future reference after all, the result of the action only being visible in the future (as argued by AMEIS 1868a: 65, 1868b: 52-53, AMEIS & HENTZE 1884: 70). The suggestion that the future-subjunctive form here might have some potential nuance “why you cannot take...” (as suggested by LA ROCHE 1870a: 57 and LEAF 1886: 59), seems less plausible to me.⁴¹ BEKKER’s correction would obviously solve the problem of the missing modal particle, but this alone is not sufficient to justify the correction. The instance remains problematic.

(EX.20) (379) εἰ δέ ποτ’ ἔς γε μίαν βουλευσομεν, οὐκέτ’ ἔπειτα
(380) Τρωσὶν ἀνάβλησις κακοῦ ἔσσεται οὐδ’ ἠβαιόν. (*Iliad* 2,379-380).

“If one day we can agree on one plan, then no longer shall there be removal of evil for the Trojans, not even for a short period of time.”

⁴¹ The issue was not addressed in KIRK (1985: 155), nor did the editions by MONRO & ALLEN (1902 *on this passage*) or VAN THIEL (2011: 32) mention the correction in their apparatus.

In this conditional clause, the future-subjunctive βουλεύσομεν has no MP, not only because it is a future-subjunctive form, but because it is combined with ποτέ. The undefined temporal adverb ποτέ “once, at one undefined moment” is present and makes the statement less secure and more undefined: ποτέ is combined 46 times with a future-subjunctive, future-desiderative, subjunctive or optative,⁴² and in 39 instances there is no modal particle (DE DECKER 2015: 217).⁴³ As such, we have analysed all instances of the conditional clauses and will now proceed to other elements causing the absence of the MP.

13.5. The repeated actions

A subjunctive or optative that describes a repeated action, is not used with an MP. We have four examples of this (188, 198, 198, 215) in our corpus.

(EX.21) (198) ὃν δ’ αὖ δῆμου τ’ ἄνδρα ἴδοι βοόωντά τ’ ἐφεύροι,

(199) τὸν σκῆπτρῳ ἐλάσασκεν ὀμοκλήσασκέ τε μύθῳ: (*Iliad* 2,198-199).

“Whichever man from the people he would see and find shouting, he would drive forward with the sceptre and chastise with (this) word.”

In this instance Homer describes how Odysseus would chastise and drive forward any Greek soldier whom he saw withholding from battle. The combination of an optative and an iterative form is common,⁴⁴ but it is important to note that it is not the optative per se which has the iterative notion, but the con-

⁴² The instances are *Iliad* 1,166; 1,205; 1,213; 1,234; 1,240; 1,340; 2,97; 2,325; 2,379; 4,164; 4,182; 6,448; 6,459; 6,462; 6,479; 7,87; 7,91; 7,343; 8,148; 8,150; 9,495; 10,453; 13,625; 14,481; 15,40; 18,283; 22,106; 23,575 and *Odyssey* 1,308; 2,76; 2,137; 2,203; 2,256; 2,342; 3,216; 8,461; 17,249; 18,141; 19,22; 19,81; 21,324; 21,403; 24,196.

⁴³ The instances are *Iliad* 1,213; 1,234; 1,240; 1,340; 2,97; 2,325; 2,379; 4,182; 6,459; 6,462; 6,479; 7,87; 7,91; 7,343; 8,148; 8,150; 9,495; 10,453; 13,625; 14,481; 15,40; 18,283; 22,106; 23,575 and *Odyssey* 1,308; 2,137; 2,203; 2,256; 2,342; 8,461; 17,249; 18,141; 19,22; 19,81; 21,324; 21,403; 24,196.

⁴⁴ For the co-occurrence of optatives and iterative forms, see especially STOLPE (1849: 36-39), TYN (1860: 677-681, 685-686), DELBRÜCK (1897: 62-63), KLUGE (1911: 56-57), SCHWYZER & DEBRUNNER (1950: 335-336, explaining this form as a past potential), ZERDIN (2002: 117-118), and PAGNIELLO (2007, also interpreting this form as a past potential). MONRO (1891: 279, 282-283) described the iterative use of the optative, but did not link it with the iterative forms, while KÜHNER & GERTH (1898: 252-257 – discussing this specific instance as well, 1904: 427), SCHWYZER & DEBRUNNER (1950: 335-336) and CHANTRAINE (1953: 223-224) were more hesitant and ascribed to the optatives in such constructions the meaning of “possibility” rather than the notion of repetition. It is debated whether or not Homer knew the so-called *optativus iterativus* (KRÜGER 1859: 148, LANGE 1872: 373, 401, MONRO 1891: 284, CHANTRAINE 1953: 224 believed he did not know it, but BUTTMANN (1810: 502 quoting this specific instance), VON THIERSCH 1826: 611, ROST 1826: 464, MATTHIA 1827: 1005, BERNHARDY 1829: 406-407 thought the modus could have iterative notion) and more general if this optative exists at all (I would personally agree with, among others, Chantraine and SCHWYZER & DEBRUNNER in stating that it is the context and not the optative mood that decides on the iterative meaning).

text in which it appears (the facts that subjunctives can indicate an iterative action and that an optative without MP can be used for a single action prove this).⁴⁵

14. The instances with an MP

After discussing the instances without modal particle I will now address the use of the particle.

14.1. The “specific” cases

In most cases the MP refers to a specific instance (12, 29, 34, 66, 72, 81, 83, 123 (but see below), 128, 139, 155, 160, 176, 228, 229, 231, 242, 250 (but see below), 258, 332, 347, 361, 364, 366, 391, 488 (but see below)). Below I discuss two examples.

- (EX.22) (239) ὃς καὶ νῦν Ἀχιλῆα ἔο μέγ’ ἀμείνονα φῶτα
 (240) ἠτίμησεν: ἐλὼν γὰρ ἔχει γέρας αὐτὸς ἀπούρας.
 (241) ἀλλὰ μάλ’ οὐκ Ἀχιλῆϊ χόλος φρεσίν, ἀλλὰ μεθήμων:
 (242) ἦ γὰρ ἂν Ἀτρεΐδῃ νῦν ὕστατα λωβήσαιο: (*Iliad* 2,239-242).

“He who now has dishonoured Achilles, a hero much more valiant than he himself. He holds his gift after taking it away and robbing it himself. But there is no anger in Achilles’ heart and he is forgiving. Otherwise, for certain, son of Atreus, you would now have committed your last outrage.”

In this passage Thersites insults Agamemnon by saying that if Achilles had really wanted, he (Ag) would have committed his last outrage and he (Ach) would have killed him during their fight. The verb form λωβήσαιο has a modal particle, because it clearly refers to a single and specific instance, near to speaker and addressee. This closeness to the speaker and the current situation is additionally expressed by the adverb νῦν (as in 12, 29, 66).

- (EX.23) οὐ τοι ἀπόβλητον ἔπος ἔσσειται ὅττι κεν εἶπω (*Iliad* 2,361).
 “A word that I will speak will not be thrown away (i.e. shall not be vain).”

In this instance εἶπω is used with a modal particle because it refers to a word that the speaker is about to speak and thus refers to a single action in the presence of speaker and hearer (see also 139).

14.2. Speech versus narrative

A very remarkable fact is that the modal particle is used much more often in speech than in narrative. In our corpus we have 29 instances with an MP in

⁴⁵ Already MATTHIA (1827: 1005-1006) pointed this out.

a speech and 66 without one (31%), against 3 instances with and 13 without in narrative. In the *Iliad* (without Books 2 and 10) the distribution is 668 instances with and 1378 without one in the speeches (33%) against 78 with one and 283 without it in narrative (21%). This is remarkable, but agrees with the research hypothesis. As speeches (mostly) refer to events that happen(ed) near to speaker and hearer, it is expected that the verbs describing these events would more often receive an MP than the verbs describing events in a more distant past and/or events that were more removed from the audience.

After having discussed the rules applying to the use of the MP, I now proceed to the exceptions, namely cases where the MP appears in contradiction with the rules described above.

14.3. Purpose clauses

In affirmative purpose clauses the MP is missing in most instances, but not always.⁴⁶ If we assume that many purpose clauses with an MP were in origin other subordinate clauses (relative or temporal) with a nuance of purpose, the use of the MP could be explained. Often it is not straightforward to decide whether one is dealing with a relative, temporal or purpose clause, or a relative clause with a final nuance. In many relative clauses introduced by a relative pronoun, one could notice a purpose meaning as well. As they could appear with an MP, the use of the MP appeared also in clauses with this purpose nuance.⁴⁷ From there the particle intruded also into the “normal” purpose clauses and became the standard in the Attic inscriptions. WEBER’s statement that most purpose clauses with an MP occur in the *Odyssey* (1885: 35) is only partly true, since there are also instances in the *Iliad*: there are 29 instances of an MP in a purpose clause against 252 without one (10%) and in the *Odyssey* there are 48 instances with an MP and 267 without one in a purpose clause (15%). As was stated above, we have two purpose clauses with an MP in our corpus

It is very likely that phrases where both relative and purpose nuances coincided caused the particle use to expand towards “genuine” purpose clauses, and in the two instances in our corpus both nuances can still be seen and one relative clause .

⁴⁶ KRÜGER (1859: 102-103), CURTIUS (1864: 242), MONRO (1891: 260-264), KÜHNER & GERTH (1904: 385) and CHANTRAINE (1953: 266-273) noted the possibility that purpose clauses could have an MP, but did not state that this use was rare in epic nor did they link the use explicitly with the other uses of the conjunctions involved.

⁴⁷ This had been suggested already by von NAEGELSBACH (1834: 7). See also WEBER (1884) and SCHWYZER & DEBRUNNER (1950: 672). For ὄppα see WEBER (1884: 17-18) and for ὠς WEBER (1884: 11-13).— Generally, it has been argued that the MP was used with these adverbs when they had temporal and/or relative value, but not when they had final meaning (VON THIERSCH 1826: 655-656, ROST 1826: 478-479).

(EX.24) (439) ἡμεῖς δ' ἀθρόοι ὧδε κατὰ στρατὸν εὐρὸν Ἀχαιῶν
 (440) ἴομεν ὄφρα κε θᾶσσον ἐγείρομεν ὄξυν Ἄρηα.» (*Iliad* 2,439-440)

“Let us gather and go through the broad army of the Achaeans until/so that we can raise fast Ares (i.e. start fighting quickly).”

In this instance the subordinate clause ὄφρα κε ἐγείρομεν can be interpreted as a temporal clause “until”, but also as a final one (“so that, until”). For the Greek ear both meanings were probably present and examples such as this one probably contributed to the feeling of the speakers that a modal particle could also be used in clauses with these adverbs when the adverbs had final meaning. The same applies for the other example 385 (with ὡς).

14.4. *Similia*

Similia tend not to have a modal particle, and yet there are several instances where the MP appears. In almost all instances the mood involved is the subjunctive (potential and counterfactual optatives and indicatives are very rare in these epic comparisons, as they describe real scenes from everyday life). In most of these passages one could remove the MP without too much “trouble”, but the cumulative evidence remains and one has to ask how the transmission could have gone “wrong” on so many instances. There is no easy answer to this, but one could try to argue that since temporal, relative and conditional clauses with the subjunctive often take the MP, this use could have spread from the “normal” passages to the *similia*. Alternatively, one could try to argue that many *similia* appear in narrative (but certainly not all of them) and that that fact contributed to the less frequent use of the modal particle.

14.5. Future-subjunctives

Finally, I have to address also the fact that some (or better put a substantial amount of) future-subjunctives are constructed with an MP after all. I suspect that the appearance of these forms in contexts where the optative and “genuine” subjunctive forms could be used with a modal particle led to the extension of the modal particle to these future-subjunctive forms as well. Of the six instances with a modal particle in our corpus, five appear in a conditional clause, where the aorist subjunctive is often used with a modal particle as well. In the entire *Iliad* it is striking to note that the future-subjunctives are more used with a modal particle in subordinate clauses than in the main clauses. When we compare the future-subjunctives with the future-desideratives and the aorist subjunctives (the verb forms they are very closely related to), we note some striking parallels they are in line with what CHANTRAINE 1953: 206-212 had already suggested). First I give the overall figures of the future-subjunctives compared with the future-desideratives and aorist subjunctives, then those in

the main clause, and followed by the ones in the subordinate clauses; future-desideratives are mostly found in the main clause and almost never receive a modal particle, whereas aorist subjunctives appear much more often in subordinate clauses where the presence of the modal particle is slightly higher than the absence. For completeness I also added the subjunctive forms that could be both present or aorist. While the percentage of future-subjunctive forms with a modal particle is still lower than that of the aorist-subjunctive, we do note that the percentage is considerably higher in those contexts where its use resembles that of the aorist subjunctive and lower where it has the same use as the future-desiderative. It is therefore probable that they were initially not used with a modal particle, but slowly and steadily started to use it when they were used in contexts where other verb forms would regularly use one as well (mostly in temporal, relative and conditional clauses).

TENSE/MOOD	MP	No MP	% MP
FUTURE SUBJUNCTIVES	72	374	16
FUTURE DESIDERATIVES	8	350	2
AORIST SUBJUNCTIVE	217	266	45
SUBJUNCTIVE UNDEFINED	11	19	37

Table 7: overall figures future-subjunctives, future-desideratives, aorist subjunctives, undefined subjunctives

TENSE/MOOD	MP	No MP	% MP
FUTURE SUBJUNCTIVES	11	212	5
FUTURE DESIDERATIVES	5	301	2
AORIST SUBJUNCTIVE	9	39	19
SUBJUNCTIVE UNDEFINED	1	9	

Table 8: figures future-subjunctives, future-desideratives, aorist subjunctives, undefined subjunctives in the main clauses

TENSE/MOOD	MP	No MP	% MP
FUTURE SUBJUNCTIVES	61	129	32
FUTURE DESIDERATIVES	3	49	6
AORIST SUBJUNCTIVE	211	171	55
SUBJUNCTIVE UNDEFINED	13	14	48

Table 9: future-subjunctives, future-desideratives, aorist subjunctives, undefined subjunctives in a subordinate clause.

TENSE/MOOD	MP	No MP	% MP
FUTURE SUBJUNCTIVES	0	33	
FUTURE DESIDERATIVES	0	0	
AORIST SUBJUNCTIVE	0	50	
SUBJUNCTIVE UNDEFINED	0	2	

Table 10: future-subjunctives, future-desideratives, aorist subjunctives, undefined subjunctives in the “negative purpose clauses”.

15. Conclusion

In this article I addressed the use of the modal particle in *Iliad* 2,1-493 (the part of Book 2 before the Catalogue of Ships starts). As is known, the use of the modal particle is strictly regulated in Attic Greek and in most other Greek dialects (although there are differences between Attic and some other dialects), but is much less clear in Homeric Greek. In this book there were about 110 subjunctive, optative and modal indicative forms to analyse. First, I determined the corpus addressing both transmission problems (is the modal particle metrically secure?) as comparative-philological issues (which mood and tense does this form have and were there variants of this form). In doing so I catalogued the forms according to tense and mood, but also created two separate categories, the future-subjunctives (the verbs for which the sigmatic future is metrically equivalent to the subjunctive of the sigmatic aorist) and the future-desideratives (the sigmatic future forms of the verbs that do not have a sigmatic aorist or the verbs for which the sigmatic future differs from that of the sigmatic subjunctive aorist forms, such as the *verba liquida* or the semi-deponent verbs). In addition I also addressed two other issues that emerged, that of the short vowel subjunctives and of the endings in *-εἰ* (which in some Ionic dialects can act as subjunctive ending and in other dialects as optative aorist ending). After determining the corpus, I proceeded to the actual analysis, building on previous analyses by HARTUNG, VON BÄUMLEIN, MONRO and CHANTRAINE and combining them with ALLAN’s axes of modality. My research hypotheses were (i) that the modal particle was incompatible with the deontic and jussive axis (thus never appearing in voluntative-desiderative and exhortative contexts), (ii) that it was used in specific instances referring to events close to speaker and hearer and (iii) missing when repeated actions, events in a more remote past and generic-timeless statements were related, and when a verb form was preceded by another verb form that had already “received”. The overall data of the corpus confirmed these hypotheses: this explains the absence with the future-desiderative forms, wishes, negative purpose clauses and exhortative forms, the relatively uncommon use in positive purpose clauses and with future-subjunctive forms, why *similia* rarely use the particle, why conditional, relative and temporal clauses with iterative meaning

are used without a particle and why conditional clauses with the optative prefer not to have the particle either (as they maintain in most instances their original voluntative meaning). It also explains why the particle use is more common in speeches than in narrative (as speeches are by definition closer to the speaker and audience) and why it can be used to emphasise statements and most importantly, why it is used in contexts where specific individual cases are discussed.

This is not to say that there are no exceptions, sometimes these are explainable by the fact that the strict distinctions between the different type of mood and tense (the future-subjunctives having both the notion of future and subjunctive, they sometimes “take over” the particle use of the “genuine” subjunctives) or between the types of sentences were not always clear (as is sometimes the case for relative, temporal and purpose clauses), but this explanation cannot account for all the exceptions. Alternatively, one could try to argue that the particle use in epic Greek was in the process of becoming grammaticalised and that this fact caused some “infractions” on the rules, but this does not explain either why the exceptions occurred in those instances where they occurred.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Online resources:

Thesaurus Linguae Graecae: <http://stephanus.tlg.uci.edu/Iris/inst/tsearch.jsp>

Chicago Homer: <https://homer.library.northwestern.edu/html/application.html>

Perseus: <http://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/collection?collection=Perseus:collection:Greco-Roman>

AHRENS, Rudolph (1852), *Griechische Formenlehre des Homerischen und Attischen Dialektes*. Göttingen: Vandenhoeck und Ruprecht.

AKEN, Adolf Friedrich (1861), *Die Grundzüge der Lehre von Tempus und Modus im Griechischen: historisch und vergleichend aufgestellt*. Rostock: Stiller.

— (1865), *Die Hauptdata der griechischen Tempus- und Modullehre, historisch und vergleichend*. Berlin: Enslin.

ALLAN, Rutger (2013), “Exploring Modality’s Semantic Space Grammaticalization, Subjectification and the case of ὀφείλω.” *Glotta* 89, 1-46.

AMEIS, Karl Friedrich (1868a), *Ilias. Für den Schulgebrauch erklärt. Erster Band. Erstes Heft. Gesang 1-3*. Leipzig: Teubner.

— (1868b), *Anhang zu Homers Ilias Schulausgabe. I. Heft. Erläuterungen zu Gesang I-III*. Leipzig: Teubner.

— (1868c), *Anhang zu Homers Odyssee Schulausgabe. Erläuterungen zu Gesang XIX - XXIV*. Leipzig: Teubner.

- AMEIS, Karl Friedrich & Carl HENTZE (1871), *Homers Odyssee. Für den Schulgebrauch erklärt. Gesang XIX-XXIV*. Leipzig: Teubner.
- (1884), *Ilias. Für den Schulgebrauch erklärt. Gesang I-III*. Leipzig: Teubner.
- (1888), *Homers Ilias. Für den Schulgebrauch erklärt. Gesang XXII-XXIV*. Leipzig: Teubner.
- (1898), *Homers Odyssee. Für den Schulgebrauch erklärt. Gesang XIII-XVIII*. Leipzig: Teubner.
- (1901), *Homers Odyssee. Für den Schulgebrauch erklärt. Gesang XIX-XXIV*. Leipzig: Teubner.
- AMIGUES, Suzanne (1977), *Les subordinées finales par ΟΠΩΣ en attique classique*. Paris: Klincksieck.
- BARNES, Joshua (1711), *Homeri Ilias & Odyssea. Et in easdem Scholia, sive Interpretatio, Veterum*. Cambridge: Cornfield.
- BASSET, Louis (1988), “Valeurs et emplois de la particule dite modale en grec ancien. Valeurs et emplois de la particule dite modale en grec ancien.” In: Rijksbaron, Albert & Mulder, Hotze & Wakker, Gerry (eds.). *In the footsteps of Raphael Kühner*. Amsterdam: Gieben, 27-37.
- (1989), *La syntaxe de l’imaginaire: études des modes et des négations dans l’Iliade et l’Odyssée*. Lyon: Maison de l’Orient et de la Méditerranée.
- BECHTEL, Friedrich (1884), “Die inschriftlichen denkmäler des arkadischen Dialektes”. *BB* 8. 301-327.
- (1921), *Die griechischen Dialekte. Erster Band. Der lesbische, thessalische, böotische, arkadische und kyprische Dialekt*. Berlin: De Gruyter.
- (1923), *Die griechischen Dialekte. Zweiter Band. Die westgriechischen Dialekte*. Berlin: De Gruyter.
- (1924), *Die griechischen Dialekte. Dritter Band. Der ionische Dialekt*. Berlin: De Gruyter.
- BEKKER, Immanuel (1858), *Carmina Homerica. Volumen Prius. Ilias*. Bonn: Marcus.
- (1863), *Homerische Blätter. Erster Band. Beilage zu dessen Carmina Homerica*. Bonn: Marcus.
- BERNHARDY, Gottfried (1829), *Wissenschaftliche Syntax der griechischen Sprache*. Berlin: Duncker und Humblot.
- BERS, Victor (1984), *Greek Poetic Syntax in the Classical Age*. Yale: Yale University Press.
- BIZOS, Marcel (1961), *Syntaxe grecque*. Paris: Vuibert.
- BRÜGGER, Claude (2017), *Homer Iliad. The Basel Commentary. Book XXIV*. Translated by Benjamin W. Millis and Sara Strack. Edited by S. Douglas Olson. Berlin: De Gruyter.
- BRUGMANN, Karl (1880), “Beiträge zur conjugationslehre: Der sogenannte unechte Konjunktiv”. In: Brugmann, Karl and Osthoff, Hermann. *Morpho-*

- logische Untersuchungen auf dem Gebiete der indogermanischen Sprachen.*
Leipzig: Hirzel. Volume 3. 1-16.
- (1890), *Griechische Grammatik.* München: Beck.
- (1900), *Griechische Grammatik.* München: Beck.
- (1904), *Kurze vergleichende Grammatik der indogermanischen Sprachen.*
Strassburg.
- (1916), *Grundriß der vergleichenden Grammatik der indogermanischen Sprachen.* II.3. Strassburg: Karl Trübner.
- BRUGMANN, Karl & Albert THUMB (1913), *Griechische Grammatik.* München: Beck.
- BRUNEL, Jean (1980), “Les périodes conditionnelles du grec et le problème de l’optatif”. *BSL* 75/1, 227-261.
- BUCK, Carl Darling (1910), *The Greek Dialects.* Chicago: Chicago University Press.
- BUTTMANN, Philip (1810), *Griechische Grammatik.* Fünfte, vermehrte und verbesserte Ausgabe. Berlin: in der Myliussischen Buchhandlung.
- (1819), *Griechische Schulgrammatik.* Fünfte Auflage. Berlin: in der Myliussischen Buchhandlung.
- (1830), *Ausführliche griechische Sprachlehre.* Erster Band. Berlin: Dümmler.
- (1854), *Griechische Grammatik.* Berlin: Dümmler.
- BYBEE, Joan, Revere PERKINS & William PAGLIUCA (1994), *The Evolution of Grammar. Tense, Aspect and Modality in the Languages of the World.* Chicago: Chicago University Press.
- CAMERER, Ruth (1968), “Über den emphatischen Grundwert des Partikels ἄν”. *Glotta* 46, 106-117
- CAUER, Paul (1890), *Homeri Ilias in Scholarum Usum edidit Paulus Cauer.* Pars I: Carm. I - XII. Leipzig: Freytag.
- CHANTRAINE, Pierre (1948), *Grammaire homérique.* Paris: Klincksieck.
- (1953) *Grammaire homérique. Tome II. Syntaxe.* Paris: Klincksieck.
- (1964) *Morphologie historique du grec.* Paris: Klincksieck (1948).
Deuxième édition revue et augmentée (1964).
- CHANTRAINE, Pierre & Michel CASEVITZ (2013), *Grammaire homérique. Tome I: Phonétique et morphologie.* Nouvelle édition revue et corrigée par Michel Casevitz. Paris: Klincksieck.
- (2015), *Grammaire homérique. Tome II : Syntaxe.* Nouvelle édition revue et corrigée par Michel Casevitz. Paris: Klincksieck.
- CHITIL, Claudius (1899), *Zur Konstruktion der Finalsätze im Griechischen.* Waidhausen an der Thaya: Verlag des Realgymnasiums.
- COLVIN, Stephen (2012), “The Modal Particle in Greek”. *CCJ* 62, 65-84.
- CRESPO, Emilio (1997), “Delbrück y la sintaxis de los modos”. In: Crespo, Emilio & García-Ramón, José Luís (eds), *Berthold Delbrück y la sintaxis indoeuropea hoy.* Wiesbaden, 27-62.

- CURTIUS, Georg (1864), *Griechische Schulgrammatik. Zweite Auflage*. Prag: Tempsky.
- (1880), *Das Verbum der griechischen Sprache, seinem Baue nach dargestellt*. Zweiter Band. Leipzig: Hirzel.
- DEBRUNNER, Albert (1921), “Das hellenistische Nebensatziterativpräteritum mit ἄν”. *Glotta* 11, 1-28.
- DE DECKER, Filip (2015), *A Morphosyntactic Analysis of Speech Introductions and Conclusions in Homer*. PhD thesis. Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München. Online publication: <https://edoc.ub.uni-muenchen.de/17995/>
- (2021), “A look at an alleged morpho-syntactic isogloss between Greek and Anatolian: the modal particle in epic Greek.” In: Giusfredi, Federico & Simon, Zsolt (eds.), *Studies in the languages and language contact in Pre-Hellenistic Anatolia*. Barcino Monographica Anatolica, Vol. 17. Barcelona, 101-189.
- DE HAAN, Ferdinand (2006), “Typological approaches to modality”. In: Frawley, William (ed), *The expression of modality*. Berlin: De Gruyter, 26-63.
- DELBRÜCK, Berthold (1871), *Syntaktische Forschungen I. Der Gebrauch des Conjunctivis und Optativis im Sanskrit und Griechischen*. Halle: Verlag der Buchhandlung des Waisenhauses.
- (1879), *Syntaktische Forschungen IV. Die Grundlagen der griechischen Syntax*. Halle: Verlag der Buchhandlung des Waisenhauses.
- (1888), *Syntaktische Forschungen V. Altindische Syntax*. Halle: Verlag der Buchhandlung des Waisenhauses.
- (1897), *Vergleichende Syntax der indogermanischen Sprachen*. II. Strassburg: Karl Trübner.
- DE MOL, Geert (2015), *Het modale partikel ἄν/κε(v)/κα*. Een bijdrage aan de Griekse Grammatica DyLEGRam. MA thesis. Katholieke Universiteit Leuven.
- DEVARIUS, Matthaeus [= Matthaios DEVARIS] (1587), *De Graecae Linguae Particulis*. Rome: Zanetti.
- DEVARIUS, Matthaeus & Reinhold KLOTZ (1835), *Matthaei Devari Liber de Graecae linguae particulis*. Edidit Reinholdus Klotz. Leipzig: Baumgärtner.
- (1842), *Matthaei Devari Liber de Graecae linguae particulis*. Edidit Reinholdus Klotz. Vol II. Reinholdi Klotz adnotationes continens. Leipzig: Baumgärtner.
- DUBOIS, Laurent (1986), *Recherches sur le dialecte arcadien I. Grammaire*. Louvain-la-Neuve: Presses de l’université.
- DUNKEL, George (1990), “Jakob Wackernagel und die idg. Partikeln *só, *ke, *kem und *an.” In: Rix, Helmut & Eichner, Heiner (eds). *Sprachwissenschaft und Philologie. Jakob Wackernagel und die Indogermanistik heute*. Wiesbaden: Ludwig Reichert, 110-130.
- (2014a), *Lexikon der indogermanischen Partikeln und Pronominalstämme*. Band 1: Einleitung. Heidelberg: Carl Winter

- (2014b), *Lexikon der indogermanischen Partikeln und Pronominalstämme*. Band 2: Lexikon. Heidelberg: Carl Winter.
- DÜNTZER, Heinrich (1866), *Homers Ilias. Erklärende Schulausgabe. Erstes Heft. Buch I-VIII*. Paderborn: Schöningh.
- EBELING, Heinrich (1885), *Lexicon Homericum*. I. A-Ξ. Leipzig: Teubner.
- EDWARDS, Mark (1991), *The Iliad: A Commentary. Books 17-20*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- FAESI, Johann Ulrich (1858a), *Homers Iliade, erklärt von J. U. Faesi*. Erster Band. Berlin: Weidmann.
- (1858b), *Homers Iliade, erklärt von J. U. Faesi*. Zweiter Band. Berlin: Weidmann.
- FRANKE, August (1861), *Über die Bildung der Futura im Griechischen*. Lingen: Sattler.
- FERNÁNDEZ GALIANO, Manuel (1993), Books XXI-XXII. In: Russo, Joseph, Manuel Fernández Galiano Albert & Heubeck, *A Commentary on Homer's Odyssey. Vol. III: Books XVII – XXIV*. Oxford: Clarendon Press. 131-311.
- FROHBERGER, H. (1863), “Ueber die unterordnung mehrerer verba unter ein ἀπὸ κοινοῦ stehendes ἄν”. *Philologus* 19, 599-613.
- GERÖ, Eva Carin (2000), “The Usage of ἄν and κε in Ancient Greek: Towards Unified Description”. *Glotta* 76, 176-191.
- (2001), “Irrealis and Past Tense in Ancient Greek”. *Glotta* 77, 178-197.
- GERTH, Berthold (1878), *Grammatisch-Kritisches zur griechischen Moduslehre*. Dresden: Programm des Königlichen Gymnasiums zu Dresden-Neustadt.
- GILDERSLEEVE, Basil Lanneau (1882), “Studies in Pindaric Syntax”. *AJP* 3, 434-455.
- (1900), *Syntax of Classical Greek*. New York & Cincinnati & Chicago: American Book Company.
- GONDA, Jan (1956), *The Character of the Indo-European Moods*. Wiesbaden: Ludwig Reichert.
- GOODWIN, William (1865), *Syntax of the Moods and Tenses of the Greek Verb*. Cambridge, MA: Sever and Francis.
- HAINSWORTH, John Brian (1993), *The Iliad. A commentary III: books 9-12*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- HARTUNG, Johann (1832), *Lehre von den Partikeln der griechischen Sprache I*. Erlangen: Enke.
- (1833), *Lehre von den Partikeln der griechischen Sprache II*. Erlangen: Enke.
- HENTZE, Carl (1906), “Zur Entwicklungsgeschichte der Finalsätze auf Grund der homerischen Epen”. *Philologus* 65, 161-192.
- (1907), “Der homerische Gebrauch der Partikeln εἰ, εἶ κε und ἦν mit dem Konjunktiv”. *KZ* 41, 356-378.

- (1909), “Der homerische Gebrauch der *ei* Sätze mit dem Indikativ des Futurs”. *KZ* 42, 131-146.
- HERMANN, Gottfried (1827), *Godofredi Hermanni Opuscula. Volumen primum*. Leipzig: Gerhard Fleischer.
- (1831), *De Particula $\alpha\upsilon$ libri IV*. Leipzig: Ernest Fleischer.
- HETTRICH, Heinrich (1992), “Lateinische Konditionalsätze in sprachvergleichender Sicht”. In: Panagl, Oswald & Krisch, Thomas (eds), *Latein und Indogermanisch*. Innsbruck: Innsbrucker Beiträge zur Sprachwissenschaft. 263-284.
- (1998), “Die Entstehung des homerischen Irrealis der Vergangenheit”. In: Jasanoff, Jay, Craig Melchert & Oliver Lisi (eds), *Mír Curad. Studies in Honor of Calvert Watkins*. Innsbruck: Innsbrucker Beiträge zur Sprachwissenschaft, 261-270.
- H. M. (1832), “On Certain Constructions of the Subjunctive Mood”. *Philological Museum* 1, 96-106.
- HOFFMANN, Otto (1891), *Die griechischen Dialekte in ihrem historischen Zusammenhange. 1. Band: Der süd-achäische Dialekt*. Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht.
- (1893), *Die griechischen Dialekte in ihrem historischen Zusammenhange. 2. Band: Der nord-achäische Dialekt*. Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht.
- (1898), *Die griechischen Dialekte in ihrem historischen Zusammenhange. 3. Band: Der ionische Dialekt*. Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht.
- HOOGEVEEN, Henricus (1769), *Doctrina Particularum Linguae Graecae*. Leiden: Damme.
- HOOGEVEEN, Henricus & Christian SCHÜTZ (1813), *Henrici Hoogeveen Doctrina Particularum Linguae Graecae in Epitomen rededit Christianus Schütz*. Glasgow: Duncan
- HOOGEVEEN, Henricus & John SEAGER (1829), *Hoogeveen's Greek Particles, Abridged and Translated into English*. London: A.J. Valpy.
- HORROCKS, Geoffrey (1995). “On condition: aspect and modality in the history of Greek”. *PCPS* 221 (NS 41), 153-174.
- HOWORTH, R. H. (1955), “The Origin of the Use of $\alpha\upsilon$ and $\kappa\epsilon\upsilon$ in Indefinite Clauses”. *Classical Quarterly* NS 5, 72-93.
- JACQUINOD, Bernard (2017), “The Syntax of Greek”. In: Fritz, Matthias, Brian Joseph & Jared Klein (eds.). *Handbook of Comparative and Historical Indo-European Linguistics I*. Berlin: De Gruyter, 682-695.
- JANKO, Richard (1994), *The Iliad: a commentary. Volume 13-16*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- KIPARSKY, Paul (1968), “Tense and Mood in Indo-European Syntax”. *FL* 4, 30-57.
- KIRK, Geoffrey (1985), *The Iliad: A Commentary. Books 1-4*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

- KLUGE, Heinrich (1911), *Syntaxis Graecae quaestiones selectae*. Inauguraldissertation Berlin.
- KRISCH, Thomas (1986), *Überlegungen zur Herkunft und Entwicklung der irrealen Konditionalsätze des Altgriechischen*. Innsbruck: Innsbrucker Beiträge zur Sprachwissenschaft.
- KRÜGER, Karl Wilhelm (1845), *Griechische Sprachlehre für Schulen*. Berlin: Krügers Verlagsbuchhandlung.
- (1846), *Griechische Sprachlehre für Schulen. Erster Theil: über die gewöhnliche, vorzüglichweise die attische Prosa. Zweites Heft: Syntax*. Berlin: Krügers Verlagsbuchhandlung.
- (1853), *Griechische Sprachlehre für Schulen. Zweiter Theil: Ueber die Dialekte, vorzugsweise den epischen und ionischen. Erstes Heft: Formlehre*. Berlin: Krügers Verlagsbuchhandlung.
- (1859), *Griechische Sprachlehre für Schulen. Zweiter Theil: Ueber die Dialekte, vorzugsweise den epischen und ionischen. Zweites Heft: Poetisch-dialektische Syntax*. Berlin: Krügers Verlagsbuchhandlung.
- KÜHNER, Raphael (1835), *Ausführliche Grammatik der griechischen Sprache. Wissenschaftlich und mit Rücksicht auf dem Schulgebrauch*. Weiter Theil. Hannover: im Verlage der Hahnschen Hofbuchhandlung.
- (1870), *Ausführliche Grammatik der griechischen Sprache*. Zweite Auflage in durchaus neuer Bearbeitung. Zweiter Theil, erste Abtheilung. Hannover: Hahnsche Hofbuchhandlung.
- KÜHNER, Raphael & Berthold GERTH (1898), *Ausführliche Grammatik der griechischen Sprache. Zweiter Theil. Satzlehre*. Erster Band. Hannover: Hahnsche Buchhandlung.
- (1904), *Ausführliche Grammatik der griechischen Sprache. Zweiter Theil. Satzlehre*. Zweiter Band. Hannover: Hahnsche Buchhandlung.
- LANGE, Ludwig (1872), *Der homerische Gebrauch der Partikel EI*. Leipzig: Hirzel.
- (1873), *Der homerische Gebrauch der Partikel EI II: EI KEN/AN mit dem Optativ und EI ohne Verbum Finitum*. Leipzig: Hirzel.
- (1869), *Homerische Untersuchungen*. Leipzig: Teubner.
- (1870a), *Homer für den Schulgebrauch erklärt. Gesang I-IV*. Berlin: Ebeling & Plahn.
- (1870b), *Homer für den Schulgebrauch erklärt. Gesang V-VIII*. Berlin: Ebeling & Plahn.
- (1871), *Homer für den Schulgebrauch erklärt. Gesang XXI-XXIV*. Berlin: Ebeling & Plahn.
- (1873), *Homeri Ilias ad fidem librorum optimorum edidit J. La Roche. Pars prior*. Leipzig: Teubner.

- LATACZ, Joachim, René NÜNLIST & Magdalene STOEVE SANDT (2002), *Homers Ilias Gesamtkommentar*. Band I. Erster Gesang. Faszikel 2: Kommentar. München: Beck.
- LEAF, Walter (1886), *Homer: The Iliad*. I: Books I-XII. London: Macmillan.
- (1888), *Homer: The Iliad*. II. Books XIII-XXIV. London: Macmillan.
- (1900), *Homer: The Iliad*. I: Books I-XII. London: Macmillan.
- MADVIG, Johan (1847), *Syntax der griechischen Sprache, besonders der attischen Sprachform, für Schulen*. Braunschweig: Friedrich Dieweg und Sohn.
- MAEHLY, Jacob (1868), *Richard Bentley. Eine Bibliographie, mit einem Anhang Bentleyscher Anecdota zu Homer*. Leipzig: Teubner.
- MATTHIAE, August (1827), *Ausführliche griechische Grammatik*. Zweiter Theil. Zweite verbesserte und vermehrte Auflage. Leipzig: Friedrich Vogel.
- MEISTERHANS, Konrad (1885), *Grammatik der attischen Inschriften*. Berlin: Weidmannsche Buchhandlung.
- MÉNDEZ-DOSUNA, Julián (2018), “The Language of the Dodona Oracular Tablets”. In: Giannakis, Georgios, Emilio Crespo & Panagiotis Filos (eds.), *Studies in Ancient Greek Dialects: From Central Greece to the Black Sea*. Berlin: De Gruyter, 265-296.
- MONRO, David Binning (1891), *Homeric Grammar*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- MONRO, David & Thomas ALLEN (1902), *Homeri Opera: Iliadis libros I-XII continens*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- MUTZBAUER, Carl (1903a), “Die Grundbedeutung des Conjunctivs und Optativs und ihre Entwicklung im Griechischen”. *Philologus* 62, 388-409.
- (1903b), “Das Wesen des Optativs”. *Philologus* 62, 626-638.
- NABER, S. A. (1877), *Quaestiones Homericae*. Amsterdam. (Reprinted as separatum from *Verhandelingen der Koninklijke Akademie van Wetenschappen, Afdeeling Letterkunde, deel 11*).
- NOVOTNÝ, Eduard (1857), *Beiträge zur Lehre vom Finalsätze in der homerischen Sprache*. Prag: Druck der königlich-kaiserlichen Schulbuchdruckerei.
- NUYTS, Jan (2001), *Epistemic Modality, Language, and Conceptualization: A Cognitive-Pragmatic Perspective*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- (2006), “Modality: overview and linguistic issues”. In: Frawley, William (ed). *The expression of modality*. Berlin: De Gruyter, 1-26.
- PAGNIELLO, Frederick (2002), *The Augment in Homer*. PhD Thesis, University of Georgia at Atlanta. Electronic Publication.
- (2007), “The past-iterative and the augment in Homer”. *IF* 112, 105-123.
- PALMER, Frank (1986), *Mood and Modality*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- (2001), *Mood and Modality*. 2nd Edition. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

- PAYNE KNIGHT, Richard (1820), *Carmina Homerica, Ilias et Odyssea, a rhapsodorum interpolationibus repurgata et in pristinam formam redacta*. London: Valpi.
- PROBERT, Philomen (2015), *Early Greek Relative Clauses*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- RIJKSBARON, Albert (2002), *The Syntax and Semantics of the Verb in Classical Greek: an Introduction*. Amsterdam: Gieben.
- RIX, Helmut (1976), *Historische Grammatik des Griechischen. Laut- und Formenlehre*. Darmstadt: Wissenschaftliche Buchgesellschaft.
- (1992), *Historische Grammatik des Griechischen. Laut- und Formenlehre*. Darmstadt: Wissenschaftliche Buchgesellschaft. 2. erweiterte und verbesserte Auflage.
- RODRÍGUEZ ADRADOS, Francisco *et al.* (1986), *Diccionario griego-español*. II. Madrid: Consejo superior de investigaciones científicas.
- ROSSBACH, August & Rudolph WESTPHAL (1856), *Griechische Metrik nach den einzelnen Strophengattungen und metrischen Stilarten*. Leipzig: Teubner.
- ROST, Valentin Christian Friedrich (1826), *Griechische Grammatik*. Göttingen: Vandenhoeck und Ruprecht.
- RUIJGH, Cornelis Jord (1969), “Esquisse d’une nouvelle théorie sur ‘TE épique’”. *Mnemosyne* IV/22, 1-69.
- (1971), *Autour de “τε-épique”*. Amsterdam: Hakkert.
- (1992), “L’emploi le plus ancien et les emplois plus récents de la particule κε/ἄν”. In: Létoublon, Françoise (ed.), *La langue et les textes en grec ancien. Actes du Colloque Pierre Chantraine*. Amsterdam: Gieben, 75-84.
- SAMPANIS, Konstantinos (2011), *A Diachronic and Typological Approach to the Modern Greek Subjunctive Complementation*. PhD Thesis Salzburg.
- (2017), “The Interplay between the Future and the Subjunctive Mood in the Diachrony of the Greek Language”. In: Lambert, Frédéric, Rutger Allan & Theodore Markopoulos (eds.), *The Greek Future and its History – Le futur grec et son histoire*. Leuven: Peeters, 237-251.
- SAVELSBERG, Martin Joseph (1867a), “Lautwandel von σ in κ. II. Im Inlaut”. *KZ* 16, 401-420.
- (1867b), “Die Aoriste ἔδωκα, ἔθηκα, ἤκα”. In: [no editor] *Symbola philologorum Bonnensium in honorem Frederici Ritschelii collecta*. Leipzig: Teubner, 505-528.
- SCHULZE, Wilhelm (1885), “Zum Dialect der ältesten ionischen Inschriften”. *Hermes* 20, 491-494.
- Schwyzler, Eduard (1939), *Griechische Grammatik auf der Grundlage Karl Brugmanns Griechischer Grammatik*. München: Beck.
- SCHWYZER, Eduard & Alfred DEBRUNNER (1950), *Griechische Grammatik. Teil II. Syntax*. München: Beck.

- SLOTTY, Julius (1915), *Der Gebrauch des Konjunktivs und Optativs in den griechischen Dialekten. I. Der Hauptsatz*. Göttingen: Universitätsbuchdruckerei von F.A. Huth.
- SMYTH, Herbert (1894), *The Sounds and Inflections of the Greek Dialects. I. Ionic*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- SMYTH, Herbert & Gordon MESSING (1956), *Greek Grammar*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- SPITZER, Johannes (1883), *Lautehre des arkadischen Dialektes*. Kiel: Schmidt & Klaunig.
- STIER, Hermann (1869), “Die Bildung des Conjunctivs bei Homer”. *CS* 2, 125-140.
- STOLPE, August (1849), *Iterativorum Graecorum vis ac natura ex usu Homeri atque Herodoti demonstrata*. Bratislava: Klein.
- TABACHOVITZ, David (1951), *Homerische ei Sätze. Eine sprachwissenschaftliche Untersuchung*. Lund: Gleerup.
- TICHY, Eva (2002), “Gr. οἴσειν, lat. *ūtī* und die Mittelzeile der Duenos-Inschrift”. *Glotta* 78, 179-202.
- TÝN, Emanuel (1860), “Über den Gebrauch und die Bedeutung der iterativen Imperfecta und Aoriste im Griechischen”. *Zeitschrift für die österreichischen Gymnasien* 10, 677-695.
- VALGIGLIO, Ernesto (1955), *Omero. Il IX Libro dell’Iliade*. Rome: Signorelli.
- VAN DER AUWERA, Johan & Vladimir PLUNGIAN (1998), “Modality’s semantic map”. *LT* 2, 79-124.
- VAN EMDE BOAS, Evert, Mathieu DE BAKKER, Luuk HUITINK & Albert RIJKSBARON (2019), *Cambridge Grammar of Classical Greek*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- VAN LEEUWEN, Jan & Maurits Benjamin MENDES DA COSTA (1895), *Homeri Iliadis Carmina cum apparatus critico ediderunt J. Van Leeuwen J. F. et M. B. Mendes da Costa*. Leiden: Sijthoff.
- VAN POTTELBERGH, Rudolph (1939), *Over de Geschiedenis en de Beteekenis van den EI-zin in het Grieksch*. Gent Claeys-Verheughe.
- VAN THIEL, Helmut (1996), *Homeri Ilias*. Hildesheim: Olms.
- (2010), *Homeri Ilias*. Second edition. Hildesheim: Olms.
- VEKSINA, Marina (2017), “Modalized Future and Scheduled Present in Coan Inscriptions”. In: Bentein, Klaas, Mark Janse & Jorie Soltic (eds.), *Variation and Change in Ancient Greek Tense, Aspect and Modality*. Leiden. 189-217.
- VOGRINZ, Gottfried (1889), *Grammatik des homerischen Dialektes*. Paderborn: Schöningh.
- VON BÄUMLEIN, Wilhelm Friedrich (1846), *Untersuchungen über die griechischen Modi und die Partikeln κέν und ἄν*. Heilbronn: Johann Ulrich Landherr.

- VON NAEGELSBACH, Carl Friedrich (1834), *Bemerkungen zur Ilias (Buch I; II 1-483), nebst Excursen über Gegenstände der homerischen Grammatik*. Nürnberg: Stein.
- VON THIERSCH, Friedrich Wilhelm (1818), *Griechische Grammatik, vorzüglich des homerischen Dialects*. Leipzig: Gerhard Fleischer.
- (1826), *Griechische Grammatik, vorzüglich des homerischen Dialektes*. Leipzig: Gerhard Fleischer.
- VOSS, Adam (1838), *Anmerkungen und Randglossen zu Griechen und Römern von J. H. Voss, herausgegeben von Adam Voss*. Leipzig: Müller.
- WACHTER, Rudolph (2000), “Grammatik der homerischen Sprache”. In: Latacz, Joachim (ed), *Homer Gesamtkommentar*. Berlin: De Gruyter, 61-108.
- WACKERNAGEL, Jakob (1897), *Vermischte Beiträge zur griechischen Sprachkunde*. Basel: Fr. Reinhardt, Universitätsdruckerei.
- WAKKER, Gerry (1994), *Conditions and Conditionals: An Investigation of Ancient Greek*. Amsterdam: Gieben.
- WEBER, Philip (1884), *Entwicklungsgeschichte der Absichtssätze. I: Von Homer bis zur attischen Prosa*. Würzburg: A. Stuber’s Verlagshandlung.
- WEST, Martin (1998), *Homerus Ilias. Volumen I: Rhapsodiae I-XII*. Berlin: De Gruyter.
- (2000), *Homerus Ilias. Volumen II: Rhapsodiae XIII-XXIV*. Berlin: De Gruyter.
- WESTPHAL, Rudolph (1868), *Griechische Metrik von A. Rossbach und R. Westphal, neu bearbeitet von R. Westphal*. Leipzig: Teubner.
- WILHELMI, Wilhelm (1881), *De modo irreali, qui dicitur*. Marburg: Robert Friedrich.
- WILLI, Andreas (2011), “Morphosyntaktische Überlegungen zum Ursprung des griechischen Futurs”. In: Krisch, Thomas & Thomas Lindner (eds.), *Indogermanistik und Linguistik im Dialog*. Wiesbaden: Ludwig Reichert, 605-615.
- (2018), *Origins of the Greek Verb*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- WILLMOTT, Jo (2007), *The Moods of Homeric Greek*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- WRIGHT, W. A. (1884), “Bentleiana I. Notes on Homer, *Iliad* I-VI”. *JPh* 13, 122-145.
- (1885), “Bentleiana II. Notes on Homer, *Iliad* I-VI”. *JPh* 13, 145-163.
- ZERDIN, Jason (1999), *Studies in the Ancient Greek Verbs in -SKŌ*. DPhil Thesis Oxford.
- (2002), “The ‘Iterative-Intensives’ in -σκ”. *Oxford Working Papers in Linguistics* 7, 103-130.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS: This research was conducted at the Università degli Studi di Verona during the project *Particles in Greek and Hittite as Ex-expression of Mood and Modality* (PaGHEMMo), which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie SKŁODOWSKA-CURIE Grant Agreement Number 101018097. I would like to thank Professor Paola COTTICELLI-KURRAS and the *doctores* Francesca COTUGNO, Stella MERLIN-DEFANTI, Valerio PISANIELLO (all *Università degli Studi di Verona*) for their insights and the discussions I had with them on this topic, and would also like to express my gratitude to the editor, Professor Dr. Romain GARNIER, and the reviewers of **wékeʷos* for their input, observations and suggestions for improvement. It goes without saying that all shortcomings, inconsistencies and/or errors are mine, and mine alone.